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Toward automatic decomposition of monolithic software into microservices

Conception of a methodology and its exemplary implementation

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Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have

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Amsterdam, 26/08/2020

Jakob Löhnertz

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Abstract

The microservices paradigm gains more and more traction, and many companies choose to adopt it for new developments as well as to transform existing monolithic software to be microservices-based instead. However, the latter approach bears many difficulties that involve much manual work, specifically in the early stages of such a decomposition process. Determining the boundaries between the services, where one service ends, and the next one begins, is a notoriously difficult task for which a lot of literature exists that however mainly helps with providing a framework to determine said boundaries manually, with *Domain-driven design* by Eric Evans laying the foundation for this entire domain of research.

This thesis devises a methodology that automatically generates microservice candidate recommendations for any given piece of monolithic software. To do this, four dimensions of coupling are calculated out of the input software that each construct a weighted graph with the edges resembling coupling between the units of the software. Next, the four graphs are merged into one before being clustered by specifically surveyed and assessed state-of-the-art graph clustering algorithms — the resulting clusters then resemble the microservice candidate recommendations. Additionally, a large set of numeric metrics was formulated to evaluate the output of the methodology. Finally, the devised methodology was fully implemented, with an additional graphical user interface for ease of use, to work with input Java software while being easily extensible to be able to support other platforms in the future.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Software engineering develops faster than ever; the amount of novelties in platforms, languages, operational strategies, and generally, the terminology around it gets larger and larger every day. One of the terms that gained a lot of traction in recent years is *microservices*. Many engineers talk about their benefits and challenges but the general notion is positive and the buzz is undeniable. At the end of the day, microservices are nothing more than an architectural pattern for designing back-end software. For those that actually take the step to build and deploy such an application landscape, the journey is not always straightforward. The idea is still evolving and mandates many new strategies and concepts that developers and operations have to deal with when choosing to devote their business logic to leverage microservices.

There are many good reasons to employ this pattern nowadays, specifically when dealing with ever larger growing monolithic applications that try to encapsulate their business logic without drowning the developers and engineers working on it in seemingly endless complexity that a single human cannot even fully comprehend anymore at one point.

For many companies, this oftentimes is the status quo and if the decision is made to move to a microservices-based architecture, one of the first challenges, the decomposition, is already difficult to begin with:

Defining where within the existing application, one service should end, and the next one should begin — i.e., detecting latent boundaries that partition the monolith into many smaller pieces, is a very manual and tedious task.

Thus, this thesis develops an algorithmic methodology that can assist a human software engineer in performing the aforementioned decomposition.

1.1 Problem analysis

Generally speaking, there are two ways to put a microservices-based software architecture into place. The greenfield approach, meaning that microservices are directly getting built without a preexisting application, as well as the transformation of an existing monolithic software solution into independent microservices [93]. However, this thesis focuses solely on the latter approach for a variety of reasons.

Firstly, our work leverages static and dynamic program analysis for solving the posed task. Obviously, this is not possible without an already running solution.

Secondly, while there is already some research on this topic [27], which we discuss in the *Related work* chapter, the notion of utilizing the already existing and running application is still underrepresented.

Thirdly, as Martin Fowler remarks, microservices are especially feasible with a mature workflow, domain model, operational model, etc. already in place [82, 80] which favors non-greenfield approaches as well.

The task of getting the boundaries of each microservice right is hard, especially when the teams working on the existing software are caught up in their mental models of it [43], as Fritzsche et al. confirm:

"Extracting a domain model from an application's code base can be a significant challenge. If incorrectly applied, it can lead to architectures that combine the drawbacks of both styles, monolithic architectures, and Microservices." [27]

To prevent such an outcome, we propose a semi-automated approach to assist software engineers in decomposing microservices out of an existing monolithic code base. This approach has the advantage that the mental models regarding the existing solution might be broken apart partially to offer new perspectives onto how the current software works, which was already remarked as a positive side effect of an assisted microservices decomposition approach [31]. Thus, the engineers and architects can be assisted in the first step, which is likely also the most difficult and time-consuming one due to the possible complexity of the system [27, 25], when undertaking the operation of transforming their existing monolithic solution into microservices.

Existing approaches in this domain mostly work on the basis of using graph clustering algorithms to receive a partitioning of the original monolithic software into microservice candidates [27].

Additionally, we are certain that the actual decisions should still be made by seasoned engineers and architects which is why a semi-automated solution was determined as the best option to support them in their decision making while not taking the decision making away from them (i.e., compared to an automated decomposition approach). As a consequence, everything mentioned in this section reflects itself in the following research questions of this thesis.

1.2 Research questions

Thus, we derived the following research questions:

RQ1: *"How can existing monolithic software be analyzed and used to give microservices recommendations based on it?"*

RQ2: *"Which numeric metrics are the most suitable for evaluating microservice decomposition methodologies?"*

RQ3: *"Which graph clustering algorithms are the most suitable for microservice decomposition methodologies?"*

1.3 Research methods

Firstly, the approach for the methodology is developed and validated for feasibility especially regarding its implementation. Apart from its general description in the *Related work* chapter, the approach itself is explained and devised in chapters 5 to 7.

Secondly, the foundation for the rationale behind the methodology is worked out as the approach itself is abstracted away from the topic of software decomposition and instead built upon graph theory. Precisely, this encompasses a mapping of the inputs into the methodology to their graph theoretic representation as well as the final output. Otherwise, no logic reasoning is possible to tie the results and their calculated metrics back to the inputs and the underlying subject of decomposing monolithic software into microservices in the first place. This part of the research is covered in Chapter 4.

Not only a theoretical methodology, but also an implemented proof-of-concept (PoC) are the results of this project. The latter is introduced in Chapter 8. The steps that this PoC needs to conduct are derived and tested independently via exploratory as well as confirmatory case studies in Chapter 10 to receive substantive, numeric, and results [17]. Moreover, controlled experiments are not feasible as control results with their dependent variables for the outcomes are rare and difficult to find and measure [17].

Finally, the research is validated with real-world monolithic applications. A large-scale code base provided by the company hosting this thesis as well as large open source software projects were candidates for this. The evaluation as part of Section 10 is conducted using a custom set of metrics devised in Chapter 7.

Chapter 2

Background

Three domains are mainly important for grasping the entirety of this work. General computer science knowledge is expected but the following three subjects are covered in more detail on top of it: *Software architectures*, *Software analysis*, and *Graph clustering*.

2.1 Software architectures

As seen in the *Introduction*, our work revolves around the decomposition of monolithic software into microservices. Thus, the following subsections focus on these two architectural styles for building back-end applications.

2.1.1 Monolithic applications

The term *monolithic* is derived from the Ancient Greek word *monólithos* which roughly translates to *single stone* [57]. This adumbrates already what the word is used for in software engineering, where it, specifically regarding enterprise back-end applications, describes software that is built, deployed, and executed as a single logical unit [81]. Furthermore, a monolithic application can perform every task of the given functionality within the domain of its business logic from beginning to end [73]. Usually this is implemented in a layered (e.g., UI, business logic, data access) and modular manner [81, 73].

Advantages

The notion exists that monolithic applications are more natural to work with while also being easier to design, build, and deploy specifically at the beginning of their life cycle [81, 59].

Tying into this, the operational overhead is small as not much middleware or special deployment strategies are necessary [81]. This becomes specifically apparent when compared to microservices in the following subsection.

Their performance is usually better compared to architectures dependent on inter-process communication [38].

Disadvantages

Even if the monolithic application is built modular and in layers, the codebase and most likely, its complexity can just grow over time. The engineer is in the end just fighting against it, becoming a *big ball of mud*, which starts to exceed the mental capabilities of a human engineer [53, 22, 25].

A monolithic application is deployed as a whole which hinders independent life cycles regarding the modules within the application [81]. Specifically in agile software development structures, this can cause immense conflicts when trying to release new versions of the application.

Finally, related to the previous disadvantage, scalability is also problematic as the only option once the application needs to be scaled is to replicate it into another instance and balance incoming load onto the instances — even if only a tiny module within the monolith might have needed any scaling in the first place [81, 53].

2.1.2 Microservices-based applications

Microservices are essentially about building an application "*as a suite of small services, each running in their own process and communicating with lightweight mechanisms, often an HTTP resource API*" [81] — a microservice is developed and deployed independently in a distributed manner. Each service should be built around one business capability following the *single responsibility principle* [53, 49]. Furthermore, each microservice should be responsible for the data it governs, avoiding any overlaps with other services [81].

Advantages

As mentioned, microservices-based architectures allow for better decoupling of software development life cycles between business capabilities [81]. This enables different teams or even individual developers to work at different velocities, as dictated by the type and complexity of the developed functionality.

Once the foundation of the architectural design is established, it is a lot more effortless to keep functionalities decoupled as they are not even part of the same process once running.

Moreover, it is easier to incorporate multiple programming languages into the application landscape that fit the tasks the best. In the end, each service just offers an external API for the others to use and consume, which is agnostic with regard to the programming language as long as it adheres to the contract provided by the interface specification.

Finally, the scalability of microservices is far better compared to monolithic applications. When leveraging features of cloud computing, just services that are in need of scaling can be scaled instead of the entirety of the application.

Disadvantages

In contrast to monolithic applications, microservices introduce a non-negligible amount of overhead. Firstly, the architectural style is geared toward agile software development, which by itself mandates a certain organizational setup.

Secondly, the development demands other patterns in terms of e.g., error-handling and data management compared to a monolithic software design.

The deployment is more fine-grained and usually encompasses many cloud computing facilities such as *Infrastructure as a Service* (IaaS) together with certain topics completely unheard of in monolithic architectures such as *service discovery* which is dealing with the task of each service knowing where and how to reach the others [53].

The overhead on inter-service communication via a network is almost always more significant than regular function calls, especially when considering serialization and deserialization before and after every inter-service call [38, 53].

Designing microservices, similarly to a modular monolithic design, is a grand task. However, the boundaries need to be defined even more strictly as migrating certain functionality and data later on has a bigger impact than doing the same in a monolithic application, since data can oftentimes stay where it is in a monolithic architecture.

The interfaces between services need more care than interfaces in a monolithic application due to their distributed nature that can lead to performance and fail-over problems a lot more likely as a network is acting in between.

Finally, Conway's law [10] is more important than ever in a microservices landscape as overly dependent life cycles between services will lead to nothing more than a *distributed monolith* in the long run.

In summary, the larger and more complicated the underlying business logic becomes, the more an application can benefit from a microservices-based architecture. Specifically when developing the overarching application in agile teams, microservices offer natural boundaries for this organizational structure. When looking at the disadvantages of them, the question of where to draw the boundaries between

microservices is especially difficult, yet it is what this thesis revolves around as it can benefit from algorithmic assistance to the work of human software engineers a lot.

2.2 Software analysis

As the goal was set that no further user input should be required by our methodology, it has to extract information out of the inputs on its own. Thus, various types of program analysis are leveraged to algorithmically collect data that can be used as the input for the methodology.

2.2.1 Static program analysis

The term *static program analysis* is best defined by comparing it to *dynamic program analysis* — instead of monitoring the program as it is running, the code, in many possible facets, is analyzed without actually executing it. While static program analysis has many categories [68], the two sub-categories relevant to this work are *call graphs* and *semantic analysis*. The latter has its roots in *natural language processing* especially in the way that it is utilized by our methodology.

Call graph generation

Generally, a call graph consists of "*nodes that are the routines of the program and directed arcs that represent calls from call sites to routines*" [29]. Those graphs can be created via static as well as dynamic program analysis, while the latter is covered in subsection 2.2.2. In an object-oriented program, the routines would represent methods or even entire classes [30].

The two basic ways to represent the weight $W(e_i) \in \mathbb{R}$ of a weighted edge $e_i \in E$ as part of a call graph $G = (V, E)$ are *execution counts* and *execution times* although *execution times* are only measurable via dynamic program analysis [29].

However, in our approach, the static program analysis that we employ has auxiliary purposes since other types of program analysis, particularly dynamic program analysis, will seldom yield a complete graph theoretic representation of the analyzed program [29], such that each routine from the input program $r_i \in R$ is part of the output graph $G = (V, E)$ as a vertex $\forall r_i \in V$ while each *execution* $x_i \in X$ is an edge $\forall x_i \in E$ connecting two such vertices $x_i = (r_1, r_2)$, $r_1 \in V$, $r_2 \in V$.

We utilize static program analysis without *execution counts*, which does not yield a weighted graph, allows us, however, to have a holistic weighted call graph when merging two or more non-holistic call graphs, weighted or not (e.g., when another was constructed with dynamic program analysis). This is discussed in the chapter *Extracting coupling information from software*.

2.2.2 Dynamic program analysis

Next to *static program analysis*, one can also analyze the behavior of an application while it is running; this is called *dynamic program analysis* [18]. The reasons to utilize *dynamic program analysis* are manifold, to gather information about runtime performance, memory usage, or debugging [18]. Another application is the creation of a call graph as discussed in subsection 2.2.1. For those and other reasons, the process of generating a *dynamic call graph* is interesting to our work.

Call graph generation

In addition to the aforementioned reasons to create a *static call graph*, a *dynamic call graph* can provide other useful information. To discover where the most data flows within the monitored application is a main application of this process [29]. The common approach is to build a weighted and optionally directed graph to represent the call graph. The optional directions are the directions the routines invoke each other and e.g., *execution counts* or average *execution times* as the weighted edges [29]. Specifically the latter can only be recorded during the runtime of the application, however for our work only *execution counts* are used as the edge weights. The general problem with *dynamic program analysis* however is that one first has to run the application that is to be analyzed and secondly the fact that there is generally no guarantee that every part of the application has been invoked even when analyzed for a large amount of time which may result in a non-holistic *dynamic call graph* [29].

2.2.3 Semantic similarity calculation

Calculating the semantic similarity between two documents is a traditional discipline in the domain of natural language processing (NLP). The similarity value usually ranges from $[0.0, 1.0]$ — a percentage [63].

As anthropogenic source code largely consists of natural language, e.g., in the form of identifiers, variable names, and comments, it can be semantically analyzed as well.

The basic steps to calculate semantic similarity between documents in any given corpus (a *corpus* is a collection of *documents*) as a mathematical process are [63]:

1. Tokenization
2. Stop word filtering
3. Normalization
4. Vectorization

5. (Optional) Relevance weighting
6. (Optional) Latent semantic indexing (LSI)

Similarity calculation

All of the above-mentioned steps have to be performed for every document in the corpus until the resulting vectors can be run through a function that calculates their similarity. A common approach for this is the *cosine similarity* which calculates the cosine of an angle θ between two input document vectors that are part of the corpus $\{\vec{d}_1, \vec{d}_2\} \in C$ [63]:

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\vec{d}_1 \cdot \vec{d}_2}{\|\vec{d}_1\| \|\vec{d}_2\|}$$

Tokenization

The goal of the first step is to retrieve a list of terms (i.e., words) of a given document in the corpus $\forall t_i \in D_i, D_i \in C$. Importantly, each document D_i is a sequence, not a set (i.e., allows the repetition of elements). Otherwise, the 5th step would not work, as shown later. Punctuation characters are stripped from the document, and the text gets split, for instance, on spaces [63].

Stop word filtering

Language naturally contains terms that do not carry much information. Those are called *stop words* [63]. Common examples from the English language are words such as: *the, and, or* etc. The useful semantics can be found in the words that are left after filtering out such *stop words*.

Normalization

This refers to the process of removing the endings of all terms in a given document $\{t_i \in D_i \mid \text{normalization}(t_i)\}$ that is part of the corpus $D_i \in C$ [63].

The rationale of this step is to normalize the semantics of the terms — $\{\text{organization, organizer, organizing}\}$ essentially encapsulate the same semantic meaning of their *lemma*: *organize*. If not normalized, a purely mathematical approach, which is utilized here, will not capture the common denominator of those terms. Consequently, each term is stripped of its ending. There are two major approaches to do so: *lemmatization* and *stemming* [54].

The *lemma* of a word is its *canonical form*, its base form [54]. Thus, *lemmatization* describes the process of normalizing words to their *lemmata* [54].

The other variant, the *stemming*, describes a similar process with the same goal that instead just strips common endings in the respective language. Therefore, *lemmatization* is objectively the better, albeit more complex, approach as it captures the actual base form of a word while also being less error-prone. A good example are the English words: $\{runs, running, ran\}$. It becomes apparent that in this example, the *stemming* approach cannot correctly normalize the word *ran*, compared to the *lemmatization* approach.

Ergo, if possible, *lemmatization* is preferred over *stemming*.

Vectorization

Since the described process is mathematical in nature, the sequence of terms out of each document of the corpus needs to be converted to numerical representations of themselves. Precisely, this step involves constructing a term-document matrix with the all terms contained in the corpus $\forall t_i \in \bigcup C$ as the rows and all the documents in the corpus $\forall D_i \in C$ as the columns. It is filled with either a 0 if a term of a given row does not appear in the document of that column or a 1 if it does appear:

$$\mathbf{t}_i^T \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \mathbf{d}_i \\ \downarrow \\ \begin{bmatrix} td_{1,1} & \dots & 1 & \dots & td_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ td_{m,1} & \dots & 0 & \dots & td_{m,n} \end{bmatrix} \end{array}$$

Consequently, this results in a document vector $\vec{\mathbf{d}}_i$ for every column $td_{*,n}$ of the matrix, which is required for the remaining steps.

Relevance weighting

Although the resulting document vectors could already be used for the *cosine similarity* calculation, the quality of the output can still be improved by weighting every term to increase or decrease its value in the matrix per document based on its relevance for that document in relation to the whole corpus.

A common approach, that we are utilizing, is *term frequency-inverse document frequency* (*tf-idf*). The idea behind it is to increase the weight of terms that have a high *term frequency* and a low *inverse document frequency*. This tends to filter out common terms while overall improving the relevance of the terms in the corpus [61, 63]. Theoretically, one can skip the step of *stop word filtering* as *tf-idf* in the end

achieves a similar goal by not returning high values for common terms that might have been considered *stop words*.

It first independently calculates the *term frequency* for each term, such that the frequency of a term in a given document is divided by the total number of terms in that document [61]. The goal is to normalize the importance of a term owing to the fact that longer documents have a higher chance of containing the given term more often [63]:

$$tf(t, d) = \frac{f_{t,d}}{|d|}$$

Next, the *inverse document frequency* is calculated for each term, such that the logarithm of the total number of documents in the corpus is divided by the number of documents containing the term [61]. This calculation quantifies the importance of a term toward the corpus [63]:

$$idf(t, C) = \log\left(\frac{|C|}{|\{d \in C \mid t \in d\}|}\right)$$

Finally, the functions are combined to calculate the *tf-idf* value of each term on a per-document basis [61]:

$$tfidf(t, d, C) = tf(t, d) \times idf(t, C)$$

Applying *tf-idf* changes the values of the elements in the matrix from $\forall td_{m,n} \in \{td \in \mathbb{Z} \mid td \geq 0\}$ to $\forall td_{m,n} \in \{td \in \mathbb{R} \mid td \geq 0\}$ due to the two divisions involved.

Latent semantic indexing (LSI)

This last step is optional but oftentimes utilized to further improve the quality of the output of the entire process. *Latent semantic indexing* (LSI) describes the process of applying *singular value decomposition* (SVD) to the aforementioned term-document matrix [14]. The rationale in the context of the similarity calculation is to reduce the matrix with m rows and n columns to one with a set amount of z dimensions as the rows. This is supposed to reduce the effects of *synonymy* and *polysemy* [14]. Precisely, *synonymy* describes the phenomenon where different terms describe the same idea [57] whereas *polysemy* describes the phenomenon where same term describes multiple ideas [57]. After applying *LSI*, each document vector of the corpus $\vec{d}_i \in C$ has a magnitude of the previously chosen z number of dimensions $\|\vec{d}_i\|$. Consequently, the above-mentioned *cosine similarity* can be calculated.

Source code processing

The main difference when processing source code, compared to processing truly natural language occurs in the first step, the *tokenization*. Truly natural language

does not use many special characters such as braces, semicolons, or ampersands, which conversely see heavy usage in many programming languages. As a consequence, the *tokenization* is specific to the respective programming language that is being processed as different languages use a different set of control characters together with differing strategies for concatenating identifiers and variable names consisting of multiple words (e.g., camel case or snake case).

Furthermore, the *stop word filtering*, if employed, has to be tailored even more to the programming language being processed — keywords (e.g., `public`, `static`, `void`) appear in every source code document while not adding any meaningful semantic information; as such, it is useful to filter those out as part of the *stop word filtering*.

2.2.4 Evolutionary similarity calculation

Similarly to the *semantic similarity*, it can be measured how much the software development life cycles of two entities (e.g., classes) do overlap. Precisely, every entity in an application has a life cycle regarding its creation, modifications (i.e., maintenance), and eventual deletion. For instance, entities that fulfill a similar functionality or have some interfaces toward each other have a high likelihood of having *evolutionary similarity* owing to the fact that the functionality they encompass is spread over multiple entities and maintenance oftentimes incorporates changes in multiple ones.

The goal again is to get a percentage that resembles how similar the life cycles of two given entities are, in the same vein as the *semantic similarity*. Compared to the previously exhibited *semantic similarity* however, the *evolutionary similarity* has the downside of not having a renowned or standard approach to retrieve the above-mentioned percentage. We chose a generally applicable approach based on the work by Tornhill on *evolutionary similarity* [64].

Essentially, this approach is based on mining information out of version control system (VCS) data such as a Git log. Listing 2.1 depicts this with one example revision entry out of a large Git log of a real application. However, multiple of those revision entries would be analyzed to calculate *evolutionary similarity*.

Precisely, over the duration of a certain time period $[t_1, t_2]$ or the entirety of the log $[t_{min}, t_{max}]$, every revision $r \in R$ contains at least one entity (i.e., file) out of the code base at that point in time $\exists e \in r, e \in E$ that was modified (including creation and deletion) as part of the revision. Over the course of all the revisions $\forall r \in R$ in a given time period $[t_1, t_2]$, the revisions where an entity $e_1 \in E$ changed together with another entity $e_2 \in E$ are gathered:

$$R' = \{r' \in \{r \in R \mid r \in [t_1, t_2]\} \mid e_1 \in r' \wedge e_2 \in r'\}$$

Furthermore, the ratio of how many of the total revisions that modified the entity e_1

is calculated to obtain a percentage:

$$\frac{|R'|}{\{r' \in \{r \in R \mid r \in [t_1, t_2]\} \mid e_1 \in r'\}}$$

As a consequence, the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ can be shifted such that either every revision is evaluated on its own or that multiple are evaluated at a time.

Additionally, a threshold can be applied to filter out noise such that only after a certain number of shared revisions of two entities $e_1 \in E, e_2 \in E$, the revisions are added to the shared revisions R' to increase the relevance of this *evolutionary similarity* measurement [64].

The details of the utilization of this approach as part of our devised methodology are explained in chapters 4 and 5.

```
commit 7fa508ea483d45b037ee9507a6e92e5bb2118418
Author: Jakob Loehnertz <mail@jakob.codes>
Date: Tue Jun 18 11:23:33 2019 +0200

    Add the average coupling modularity to the selectable ones

2  0  ../controller/analysis/metrics/clustering/QualityAnalyzer.kt
1  0  ../model/metrics/ClusteringQuality.kt
6  3  ../frontend/src/App.vue
```

Listing 2.1: Example Git log

2.3 Graph clustering

The term *graph clustering*, sometimes also called *community detection*, describes the process of partitioning a usually undirected and unweighted or weighted graph into subgraphs [41]. The graph can optionally be directed, although many graph clustering algorithms discard this information. Important to our work is that partitions on the input graph are calculated, such that the resulting clusters do not overlap, although a subset of graph clustering algorithms exists that can generate overlapping clusters. A cluster is typically described as a group of vertices that are densely interconnected via their *intra-cluster edges* while being only sparsely connected to vertices outside of their own cluster via *inter-cluster edges* [41, 52].

Network Modularity The metric of *Network Modularity* measures the quality of a graph clustering by comparing the interconnectedness of intra-cluster vertices to their inter-cluster edges. It works on unweighted as well as weighted graphs [9, 4]

and was devised in 2004 by Newman [52]:

$$Q = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij} - \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \right] \delta(c_i, c_j)$$

where

- A_{ij} is the edge weight between vertices i and j ,
- k_i and k_j is the sum of the edge weights attached to the vertices i and j ,
- m is the sum of all edge weights,
- c_i and c_j represent the clusters of the vertices i and j ,
- δ is a *Kronecker delta* function

The metric ranges on a scale of $[0.0, 1.0]$, from no clustering structure at all to a perfect clustering. Any given graph has a theoretic maximum in terms of the achievable *Modularity*. However, it is rarely 1.0 and finding the global maximum is proven to be an NP-complete optimization problem [6]. Nevertheless, the notion in literature is that values over 0.4 already resemble a strong clustering structure [52, 24].

Mean Cluster Factor The *Cluster Factor* (CF) metric calculates how good the cohesion within a cluster is compared to the coupling from within that cluster toward the other clusters [51]. This factor is a number on a scale from $[0.0, 1.0]$ with higher values being better. It bears the same proposition as the *Modularity* metric although just the value for one cluster at a time is calculated:

$$CF(c) = \frac{I(c)}{I + \frac{1}{2}J(c)}$$

while I is a function that calculates the sum of the edge weights of all intra-cluster edges of the given cluster c while J does the same for inter-cluster edges.

2.3.1 Renowned graph clustering algorithms

There are many graph clustering algorithms that were devised in this century and are considered to be state-of-the-art [41, 23, 11]. In this subsection, we discuss renowned graph clustering algorithms. The way that we utilize the exhibited graph clustering algorithms as part of this work is discussed further in Chapter 6.

Girvan-Newman [28] The *Girvan-Newman* algorithm is oftentimes seen as the most successful, wide-spread graph clustering algorithm [41]. It was released by Girvan and Newman as part of their influential 2002 paper: "*Community structure in social and biological networks*" [28]. Regardless of the title, their algorithm is generic and works on any graph network as its input [41]. Their algorithm is performing hierarchical clustering which means that every cluster that it creates can have recursive sub-clusters again [28]. Thus, this can alternatively be represented as a dendrogram [52].

It iteratively removes edges with the highest *edge betweenness centrality*, which is based on *betweenness centrality* defined in 1977 by Freeman as a metric that can be calculated for each vertex based on the idea that every two vertices of a given graph have a shortest path that connects them, the amount of how many of all those shortest paths go through any given vertex represents its *betweenness centrality* [26]. As a consequence, Girvan and Newman adapted the idea for edges and coined it *edge betweenness centrality* [28]:

$$C(e) = \sum_{s,t \in V} \frac{\sigma(s, t | e)}{\sigma(s, t)}$$

Here, $\sigma(s, t | e)$ resembles the number of shortest paths between s and t that pass through e while $\sigma(s, t)$ is the number of shortest paths between s and t .

However, since their algorithm works hierarchically, in the original implementation, the desired number of clusters has to be set beforehand which causes the algorithm to cut edges until the set amount of clusters is reached.

MCL [66] Two years before Girvan and Newman published their work, Van Dongen devised the graph clustering algorithm *MCL* [66]. It works via random walks based on Markov chains by alternating two operations on the input graph until it reaches a state of convergence regarding its clustering structure [66]. These operations are *expansion* and *inflation* [66].

The first step of *expansion* computes new probabilities for random walks for every vertex pair in the graph. Owing to the fact that random walks within clusters are usually of higher length as there are many edges to take, intra-cluster vertex pairs usually receive higher probabilities [66].

The second step, the *inflation*, then boosts and demotes probabilities further which over the course of many iterations will cause inter-cluster walks to *dry out* — Van Dongen uses the terminology of *flow* in fact [66]. Consequently, this process will form a clustering over time.

The strength of the *inflation* can be set via an input parameter that affects the granularity of the clustering and has, therefore, a similar problem as the *Girvan-Newman* algorithm. A solution to this issue is discussed in Chapter 6.

Walktrap [55] The *Walktrap* algorithm was devised in 2005 by Pons and Latapy [55] and shares similarities with *MCL*. As its name implies, it tries to compute a graph clustering by utilizing short Markov chain random walks and the idea that due to existing, albeit latent clustering structure of a given graph, those random walks are more likely to get *trapped* in said clusters [55]. The main improvement over *MCL* is better runtime complexity [55].

Clauset-Newman-Moore [9] Two years after releasing the *Girvan-Newman* algorithm, Newman released another graph clustering algorithm [52]. Its idea is based on maximizing the *Modularity* of the clustering. However, shortly after, another improved version of his new algorithm was published together with Clauset and Moore, which is the faster and generally improved version [9].

As above-mentioned, maximizing *Modularity* is an NP-complete optimization problem which led Clauset et al. to solve it via a greedy heuristic. Their algorithm starts by putting every vertex of the given graph in its own cluster, such that $\{\{v\} \mid v \in V\}$. Afterward, in a maximum of $|V| - 1$ iterations, the two clusters that share a connection and whose amalgamation increases the *Modularity* Q the most, respectively decreases it the least, are merged [9].

Eventually, this greedy algorithm will converge in a local or even global optimum regarding the *Modularity* of the computed clustering [9].

Louvain [4] The *Louvain* algorithm was devised in 2008 by Blondel et al. and is named after their university [4]. It is based on a similar premise to that of *Clauset-Newman-Moore*. The algorithm by Blondel et al. consists of two distinct phases.

Before beginning with the first phase, every vertex is placed in its own cluster. The first phase then checks for each vertex with which adjacent vertex it can merge clusters to reach a maximum increase in *Modularity*. Compared to *Clauset-Newman-Moore*, only if the *Modularity* can be actually increased, the clusters are merged [4]. All vertices are iterated over and repeatedly checked until a local optimum is reached [4].

As part of the second phase then, a new weighted graph is constructed with the clusters detected in the first phase as the vertices. The weighted edges between the new vertices are the sum of all vertices the newly connected vertices are constructed out of. Additionally, self-loops are attached to every vertex [4].

Finally, the first phase is applied to the newly constructed graph again. These two phases are then iteratively alternated until the increase in *Modularity* ends or reaches a plateau [4]. Hence, the *Louvain* algorithm is working with a heuristic as well.

Fortunato et al. showed that *Modularity* optimization suffers the problem of not being able to identify clusters of small sizes, the so-called *resolution limit problem* [24]. The main improvements proposed by Blondel et al., specifically compared

to the algorithm by Clauset et al. are better runtime complexity, and a solution to the *resolution limit problem*, that *Clauset-Newman-Moore* faces, by leveraging the aforementioned self-loops [4].

Label Propagation [58] The *Label Propagation* was devised in 2007 by Raghavan et al. as a graph clustering algorithm that works based on similar ideas to *MCL*. Just as *MCL* and in contrast to, e.g., the *Louvain* algorithm, it does not use a pre-defined fitness function. It instead works by having some labeled vertices or alternatively having all the vertices with their own label which is what we are using as no set labels are available for our graph clustering problem. The next step runs in a loop and propagates the label of a vertex to its neighbors. This will cause densely-connected vertices to reach a consensus on a certain label quickly hence forming a cluster. If a vertex has to choose between two labels, it chooses randomly, which causes this algorithm to be non-deterministic. This step is then repeated for a previously set number of iterations or until convergence is reached [58].

Infomap [62] The *Infomap* algorithm was devised in 2008 by Rosvall and Bergstrom [62]. Its process bears a similarity to the *Louvain* algorithm, although its core idea is entirely different. The similarity stems from the fact that every vertex is also assigned to its own cluster in the beginning, and that cluster is then iteratively merged when this improves the metric that the algorithm optimizes toward. However, compared to the *Louvain* algorithm, instead of *Modularity*, a *map equation* is minimized.

Precisely, *Infomap* represents the given graph as a random walk encoded via Huffman coding [33]. Additionally, each cluster receives a prefix so that the codes for the vertices can be reused in different clusters, which decreases the required amount of bits to represent the Huffman coding [62].

Finally, the phase that is reiterated over and over eventually tries to change the clusters of the vertices such that the *map equation* representing the graph clustering is minimized [62].

Chinese Whispers [3] The *Chinese Whispers* algorithm was released in 2005 by Biemann [3]. It mainly consists of an endless loop that is terminated once no better clustering can be found anymore (i.e., a local or global optimum is reached) or a predefined number of iterations has passed [3]. At first, every vertex of the given graph is put into its own cluster. Next, the vertices are iterated over in random order. Each vertex is moved to the cluster that it shares the most accumulated edge weight with [3].

Owing to the fact that this algorithm is incorporating randomness, it is non-deterministic. Moreover, it yields a flat clustering (i.e., non-hierarchical) [3].

2.4 Multi-objective optimization

As part of our evaluation, we conducted multi-objective optimization to generate optimal input settings for our methodology as well as to find interesting patterns in the experiment results.

Multi-objective optimization, also known as Pareto optimization, is an area out of the domain of mathematical optimization problems, summarized as:

"Optimization is the task of finding one or more solutions which correspond to minimizing (or maximizing) one or more specified objectives and which satisfy all constraints (if any). [...] On the other hand, a multiobjective optimization task considers several conflicting objectives simultaneously. In such a case, there is usually no single optimal solution, but a set of alternatives with different trade-offs, called Pareto optimal solutions, or non-dominated solutions." [12]

As a result, a so-called *Pareto frontier* can be approximated which contains solutions to the optimization problem that can only be improved regarding any of the given objectives by sacrificing one or more of the other objectives — they are Pareto-optimal [12].

Usually, the computation of a *Pareto frontier* is done by the means of *evolutionary algorithms*, and often more specifically via *genetic algorithms* [12].

Chapter 3

Related work

The described problem of detecting latent boundaries within existing application software for the purpose of decomposing it into microservices is a sparse research domain, especially when compared to others in computer science [27]. Nevertheless, the existing research is categorized, rated, and analyzed in the following *Literature survey*.

To add to this chapter, Fritzscht et al. conducted a literature study titled *From Monolith to Microservices: A Classification of Refactoring Approaches* (2019) [27] which looked at research in the same domain as ours. They conclude their research with:

"Our literature review has revealed a lack of systematic guidance on the refactoring process for existing monolithic applications." [27]

This underlines the relevance and importance of this area of research and the notion that there is still room for improvement.

3.1 Literature survey

The matrix 3.1 visualizes the surveyed literature via classification. Six general approaches, as well as four features, were extracted from the works. The approaches were devised by studying the available literature on the subject. In summary, other researchers were using one or more of these six approaches to answer their research questions regarding microservice decomposition out of an existing monolith. Thus, pure greenfield approaches were not targeted in the literature survey.

The evaluative signs were assigned via our intuition of the execution and results as well as the evaluation of the works in other analyzed literature. The latter approach was especially possible due to the existing work by Fritzscht et al. [27].

Approaches

In the following paragraphs, the approaches used as matrix columns are explained in more detail.

SE model analysis The term *Software Engineering (SE) models* subsumes non-source code artifacts out of the domain of SE. For instance, this category includes use case models and entity-relationship models (ERM).

Static analysis Static analysis covers any form of non-runtime analysis of the given codebase. This includes dependency graphs, class graphs, the connection of source code via shared terms (i.e., words in the identifier of classes that might tie them together), etc.

Dynamic analysis Dynamic analysis is about analyzing the existing monolithic software during its execution. This covers profiling it, tracing data inside of the application as well as analyzing access logs such as web traffic logs.

Data model analysis As one principle of the microservices architecture is about separating data stores [83], the approach to analyze the data models (e.g., schemes) of existing database tables is, generally speaking, an important one. This approach would cover the direct analysis of database tables as well as the analysis of *object relational mappings* (ORM) if those were already in use in the existing application.

VCS mining The repositories of existing solutions are usually part of a *version control system* (VCS) such as Git. Consequently, revisions and merges can be analyzed to determine e.g., the coupling of specific files, modules, or classes.

External interface analysis The external interfaces (i.e., the Web-APIs) of existing solutions can be analyzed to get a sense of existing modularization and cohesion within the solution.

Features

In the following paragraphs, the features used as matrix columns are explained in more detail.

Evaluation This column just denotes if the cited source of a row evaluated their work in any form.

Evaluation by testing Since this literature survey was focused on works that research assisted or semi-automated microservice decomposition. Theoretically, the works could be evaluated with real-world or even artificial data such as large open source projects with a monolithic architecture.

Evaluation via metrics As the area of research of this project is still rather young and sparse [36, 27], custom, as well as renowned metrics for the evaluation, are a welcomed addition to the research in this area. Additionally, evaluation via metrics improves the overall credibility of a work.

(Available) Proof-of-concept This feature is somewhat tied to the *Evaluation by testing* one as frequently a prototype (i.e., proof-of-concept) is built to test the designed methodology or algorithm. Moreover, a positive or a negative execution respectively was awarded if the prototype was publicly available (e.g., as open-source software) since it is otherwise impossible to assess.

3.2 Topic relations

Following the approaches and features extracted in the previous section, the methodologies of the works that are the closest to ours are observed in greater detail.

Gysel and Kölbener [31] were the first to release work in this area of research that is in the same vein to ours in the sense that a complete methodology is developed to convert a particular input to microservice recommendations. They initially devised the idea to build a graph out of this input that is then clustered using a graph clustering algorithm to create clusters that reflect the microservice recommendations. Future work in the domain [50, 40], together with ours, is following this idea. However, not every analyzed work uses this approach. Therefore in this subsection, only works that do use it are analyzed in detail as they relate closely in topic.

3.2.1 Analyzed inputs

Gysel and Kölbener used *SE model analysis* as their only approach — a type of input that is unlikely to be available or can only be created with much manual work, as they acknowledge themselves in their original work [31]. This fact decreases the actual usability of the devised methodology and leaves room for improvement.

Kruidenberg [40] built on top of the work and especially the implementation of Gysel and Kölbener by extending their *SE model analysis* input with *Dynamic analysis* input. Precisely, they model the input, that the implementation of Gysel and Kölbener requires and generates out of *SE models*, from data retrieved out of *Static analysis*,

Dynamic analysis, and *VCS mining*. Consequently, this approach mainly solves the problem that the original approach had regarding the availability and, respectively, the ease of creation of supported input formats.

Comparatively, Mazlami [50] devised their completely custom methodology. The foundation is still based on building and then clustering a graph, but they chose *Static analysis*, and *VCS mining* as their approaches of choice. From within the domain of static program analysis, semantically analyzing source code was devised and implemented as input together with mining evolutionary data out of version control system logs.

Instead, we utilize four distinct input dimensions for constructing a more precise weighted graph, which can then be clustered.

3.2.2 Graph clustering

Regarding the graph clustering, Gysel and Kölbener [31] only utilized two graph clustering algorithms, both of which have significant shortcomings specific to this area of research. The Girvan-Newman algorithm [28] requires the number of clusters beforehand, which is not ideal for recommending microservice candidates as the software engineers prospectively using such a tool can at best estimate that number. One advantage of automated microservice decomposition recommendations is that the algorithm might give recommendations that a human engineer would not have considered, which also affects the granularity and, therefore, the number of services (i.e., clusters). The Leung algorithm [44], on the other hand, has the disadvantage that it is non-deterministic, which might cause completely different recommendations with every execution.

Consequently, Kruidenberg [40] uses the same algorithms as his work is an extension of the one of Gysel and Kölbener.

Mazlami [50] leveraged the notion of the minimal spanning tree (MST) of the input graph to perform the clustering. Thus, their methodology is not based on state-of-the-art graph clustering algorithms but a custom approach instead. They implemented an algorithm that iteratively calculates the MST and removes the edge with the lowest similarity from the graph. However, this approach has the same problem as the Girvan-Newman algorithm [28] that Gysel and Kölbener utilized in the sense that it requires the desired number of services beforehand.

Instead, we show how to leverage heuristic optimization of the clustering and, therefore, the recommendations toward a numeric metric via a fitness function while incorporating a large set of state-of-the-art graph clustering algorithms to be able to compare them and assess which one performs the best for a given input. Thus, this removes the problem of having to define the desired number of microservices a priori.

3.2.3 Evaluative metrics

Gysel and Kölbener [31] just evaluated their initially set requirements on a custom scale of 1–3 together with a devised questionnaire to assess the quality of the recommendations. The questionnaire, however, follows no numeric metrics and just allows answers in a boolean manner, which makes it more subjective.

Mazlami [50] devised a set of six metrics that measure the output of their methodology, although some of them do not have the notion of if a higher value is better or worse (e.g., *Average Contributors per Microservice*).

Kruidenberg [40] used a combination of metrics from the works of Gysel and Kölbener [31] and Mazlami [50].

Instead, we devise an extensive set of numeric metrics that offers an objective and quantifiable view on the resulting microservice recommendations to be able to evaluate not only our methodology but the recommendations themselves as well.

Citations	Approaches						Features			
	SE model analysis	Static analysis	Dynamic analysis	Data model analysis	VCS mining	External interface analysis	Evaluation	Evaluation by testing	Evaluation via metrics	(Available) Proof-of-concept
[31]	⊕						⊖	⊕		⊕
[40]	⊙	⊙	⊙		⊙		⊙	⊙	⊖	⊕
[50]		⊙			⊕		⊙	⊕	⊙	⊕
[36]			⊕				⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖
[2]						⊕	⊕	⊕	⊙	⊙
[8]	⊕						⊙	⊙		⊖
[19]		⊕					⊙	⊙	⊙	⊖
[45]		⊙		⊙		⊙	⊖	⊖		⊖
[39]		⊙					⊖	⊖		⊖

Table 3.1: Literature survey matrix

The signs used in the matrix are defined as follows:

- An empty cell depicts that the approach or feature of that column was not utilized by the work cited in that row.
- A circle with a dot (\odot) depicts that the approach or feature of that column was utilized by the work cited in that row without any outstanding execution or results in any direction or with results that were difficult to assess.
- A plus sign (\oplus) depicts that the approach or feature of that column was utilized by the work cited in that row in a successful way.
- A minus sign (\ominus) depicts that the approach or feature of that column was utilized by the work cited in that row in a subpar way.

Chapter 4

Mapping microservice metrics to software quality metrics

As the focal point of our work is to construct a graph-theoretic representation of the input monolithic application to cluster it afterward, a rationale of how the measured dimensions of the input map to the output are deemed necessary to corroborate our research and to answer *RQ1*.

4.1 Design principles of microservices

Thus, said rationale was devised leveraging a few *design principles* of microservices [90, 81, 53]. We looked at what we deemed to be the three most important ones:

1. Services should keep inter-service communication to a minimum
2. One service should only handle one task
3. The services should have independent software development life cycles

Following this, these three items are referred to via their number in the above enumeration. Moreover, every item is discussed in more detail below.

4.1.1 Principle N° 1

As Newman and others lay out [53, 1], very *chatty* microservices are not desired due to three reasons.

Firstly, it can mean that the two services are too tightly coupled with the solution that it might have been better to merge them into one [53].

Secondly, the stability is generally worse as the architecture becomes more brittle since it always has to be assumed that inter-service communication via a network just fails due to erroneous configuration, a temporary downtime, or congestion [53, 1].

Thirdly, the performance suffers compared to native method invocations e.g., as part of a monolithic application. Communication over a network always involves latency, and the serialization and deserialization of each request and response (i.e., when utilizing JSON over HTTP) is a costly action in terms of runtime [53].

4.1.2 Principle N° 2

The second principle is ambiguous without any further elaboration owing to the fact that the term *task* has no notion of size or complexity attached to it.

Nevertheless, this idea can be seen as the focal point of the whole microservices architecture style due to the term itself — *micro*, to begin with, is vague, as Fowler discusses:

"[...] its name does lead to an unfortunate focus on the size of service, and arguments about what constitutes “micro”. In our conversations with microservice practitioners, we see a range of sizes of services." [81]

To make it entirely clear, the actual size of a microservice is not very important regarding the second principle. Instead, the idea of the *bounded context*, introduced by Evans in his influential 2004 book *Domain Driven Design* [20], is widely accepted as a practical methodology to devise the boundaries of each microservice in a given application [53, 81].

Thus, a *task* has no distinct upper limit regarding its size. One service should encapsulate one *bounded context* while trying to keep them as small as reasonably possible to still satisfy the idea of having *microservices* such that size, complexity, and maintenance stay manageable [53, 81].

Bounded contexts As mentioned, Evans created the idea of the *bounded context* defining it as follows:

"A description of a boundary (typically a subsystem, or the work of a particular team) within which a particular model is defined and applicable." [21]

while he defines *model* as:

"A system of abstractions that describes selected aspects of a domain and can be used to solve problems related to that domain." [21]

Precisely, the idea of the *bounded context* is about what parts of the domain *model* are independent enough to be *bounded contexts*, while it is even more important to define a clear interface regarding which parts of the *model* should not leave the *bounded context* and which parts have to be shared externally for the application to function and properly mirror its domain [53].

4.1.3 Principle N° 3

Since microservices are attributed to *Conway's law* [81, 16, 10] in the sense that this architectural style lends itself well to letting separate teams handle one or multiple microservices [53], it keeps the services decoupled apart from data and interfaces by having independent software development life cycles.

The more dependent the life cycles are, the more coupled the services become, and hence the longer it will take to apply feature additions, changes, or bug fixes, which can hinder the development progress.

As long as the interfaces of the services are well designed, as long as they do not change, other developers in other teams do not have to worry much that services they maintain get incompatible with other services if they or the other services change internal logic — it is in its core nothing more than the notion of proper *encapsulation* [81].

4.2 Selecting software quality metrics

All of the aforementioned principles will be violated if the boundaries of the microservices are chosen poorly. Thus, we propose a semi-automated methodology that extracts information out of the given monolithic application and devises a *good* decomposition regarding those boundaries.

Following this, we decided to map the *principles of microservices* to dimensions of the input into our devised methodology. This gives a rationale for how the eventual output of our methodology can be qualitative based on the fact that the input dimensions were carefully chosen based on what literature defines as *good* based on the principles. Virtually, the input is mapped to microservices-based architecture best practices, which allows us to reason about how and why the output of our methodology makes any sense, all based on the fact that it processes input mapped to said best practices.

Eventually, we found that four main types of coupling in software systems map to the above-mentioned principles:

1. Static coupling
2. Dynamic coupling

3. Semantic coupling

4. Evolutionary coupling

The term *coupling* is defined as:

"A measure of how closely connected two routines or modules are; the strength of the relationships between them." [5]

Precisely, the four types of coupling above are subcategories of the notion of *coupling*. These types, as well as how they map to the *principles of microservices*, are showcased in figure 4.1 and the subsections below. The details of the utilization of this mapping as part of our methodology are discussed in Chapter 5.

Figure 4.1: Mapping design principles of microservices to coupling types

We detected that three of the most important design principles of the microservices paradigm map directly to four main types of coupling.

4.2.1 Dynamic coupling

The term refers to any metric of coupling that measures how coupled components are during their runtime, hence it is recorded during the execution of a given application which ties it to *dynamic program analysis*.

For instance, counting how often a particular component calls or accesses another one is a metric described and covered in 2.2.2 as dynamic call graph generation based on *execution counts*. To clarify, a weighted and directed graph can be constructed when gathering this *dynamic coupling* metric for every single *execution count*. Hence, the weighted edges of the graph symbolize the *execution counts*.

Finally, the first principle maps to this type of coupling due to the fact that the *dynamic coupling* information can be utilized to keep communicative components from being spread over multiple microservices (i.e., being clustered together), which would otherwise violate the first principle.

4.2.2 Semantic coupling

An undirected and weighted graph is constructed out of *semantic coupling* information. Precisely, it is measured how semantically similar two components are, which causes the weighted edge in the resulting graph that connects their vertices to hold this similarity value.

Finally, the second principle maps to this type of coupling due to the fact that the *semantic coupling* information can be utilized to keep components that cover a similar (or the same) task from being spread over multiple microservices (i.e., being clustered together), which would otherwise violate the second principle.

4.2.3 Evolutionary coupling

Again, an undirected and weighted graph can be constructed out of the *evolutionary coupling* information. To be more precise, if two components change together more often, it can be inferred that their life cycles are more or less coupled. To quantify this, the approach described in 2.2.4 is leveraged to precisely calculate how *evolutionary coupled* components are (i.e., how much their life cycles overlap) which is then represented by the edge weights in the resulting weighted graph.

Finally, the third principle maps to this type of coupling due to the fact that the *evolutionary coupling* information can be utilized to keep components that currently share the same software development life cycle from being spread over multiple microservices (i.e., being clustered together), which would otherwise violate the third principle.

Chapter 5

Extracting coupling information from software

An important argument of our approach is that the coupling information exhibited in Chapter 4 are extracted out of the input monolithic application automatically without any further user input. In this chapter, it is detailed which inputs need to be supplied and how the four types of coupling are extracted out of them. Additionally, static program analysis is conducted as covered in this chapter.

Sometimes it is not possible to provide each of the four inputs, which is why at least the first and any two out of the three others have to be provided for our devised methodology to still conduct its analysis correctly.

Our methodology is focused on object-oriented programming; hence we will, from now on, use the term *class* instead of *unit* for describing the vertices of the constructed weighted graphs. The following descriptions are focused on Java applications; however, in chapter 8, we exhibit how other languages and platforms can be added to the implementation.

5.1 Static coupling extraction

As discussed in more detail in Chapter 6.1, we opt for also constructing a full static call graph which is covered in Subsection 2.2.1.

5.1.1 Walk-based approach

We utilize an approach that starts with the `main` method or methods of the given application and then recursively walks down the classes and their methods that are instantiated or invoked. Consequently, a graph with possible cycles is constructed. Both class instantiations, as well as method invocations, can be registered. However,

as part of our methodology, both will result in an edge connecting the instantiating or invoking class vertex to the one it is instantiating or invoking — algorithm 1 depicts this process.

For Java applications, both source code, as well as compiled bytecode, can be utilized as the input to algorithm 1. For both approaches, libraries exist that can access and iterate over the classes and methods as detailed in Chapter 8.

The resulting static call graph is theoretically directed in the manner that it gets constructed in algorithm 1, the first class in the class pairs that are getting returned, is the vertex the edge is pointing away from. We construct a directed, weighted graph — although the directions are ignored in most cases, as discussed in more detail in Section 8.2.

Compared to other types of program analysis, static coupling does not bear an intuitive notion of strength. To counteract this problem, we use a modification of the *Response for a class* (RFC) metric [7]. Other popular metrics, like CBO, are not as feasible as they cannot be geared toward calculating a coupling percentage between a pair of classes. RFC_α of a class counts all methods that can be invoked with a stack depth of α . The default is $\alpha = 0$, counting the directly accessible methods of a class (i.e., the compiler allows them to be called). We calculate RFC_0 values for every pair of classes that are statically coupled via method invocations or instantiations. The percentage reflects the strength of coupling between two classes c_1 and c_2 :

$$\text{RFC}_0(c_1, c_2) = \frac{|(\text{IM}(c_1, c_2) \cup \text{IM}(c_2, c_1))|}{|(\text{AM}(c_1, c_2) \cup \text{AM}(c_2, c_1))|}$$

where $\text{IM}(c_i, c_j)$ is the set of methods c_i invokes on c_j , and $\text{AM}(c_i, c_j)$ is the set of methods c_i can access in c_j .

5.2 Dynamic coupling extraction

To extract the *dynamic coupling* information, two general approaches were detected and evaluated. Both have advantages and disadvantages, which are discussed in the following subsections. However, for both approaches, the application has to be executed, which involves a lot more overhead compared to the previously exhibited *static coupling* graph construction.

As part of our methodology, we decided that the user can choose which option they want to use:

- The *sampling-based* approach has lower fidelity but also less impact on the runtime
- The *instrumentation-based* approach has high fidelity but also a large impact on the runtime

Algorithm 1: Recursive walk through classes and methods

Data: The source code or compiled code of an application**Result:** A graph with the classes as vertices and their instantiations and invocations toward others as the edges

```

1   $cg \leftarrow$  empty list of pairs of classes representing the call graph;
2   $av \leftarrow$  empty set for classes that have already been visited;
3   $cq \leftarrow$  empty queue for classes that should be visited;
4  push the classes containing main methods of the application onto queue  $cq$ ;
5  while class queue  $cq$  is not empty do
6       $vc \leftarrow$  pop class to visit next from queue  $cq$ ;
7      foreach method  $vm$  of class  $vc$  do
8          foreach class  $ic$  instantiated or invoked from method  $vm$  do
9              add pair of  $vc$  and  $ic$  to call graph list  $cg$  while recording their
               $RFC_0$  value;
10             if  $ic$  is not in set of already visited classes  $av$  then
11                 push class  $ic$  onto class queue  $cq$ ;
12                 add class  $ic$  to set of already visited classes  $av$ ;
13             end
14         end
15     end
16 end
17 return call graph list  $cq$ ;

```

Our methodology works with both approaches with the difference that the results with an *instrumentation-based* input are of better quality due to the higher input fidelity. This is further detailed in the chapter on *Steinmetz: A proof-of-concept implementation*.

5.2.1 Sampling-based approach

The first approach is more concerned with observing (i.e., monitoring) the running application from the outside. The typical way to conduct this is *sampling-based* application profiling. This means that with a preset frequency, n times per second, a sample is recorded regarding what the application is currently doing. This concerns actions such as memory usage, thread usage, which method is invoked how often, etc.

Focusing on the *Java Virtual Machine (JVM)*, as we target it with our implementation, it ships with a built-in profiler, called *Java Flight Recorder (JFR)*. The JFR is

a *sampling-based* profiler that is shipped with *OpenJDK* versions starting from 11 [79]. For other platforms and languages, different profilers are available or built-in, yet the idea to record profiling data at a certain sampling rate stays the same. Implementation details, however, differ from runtime to runtime.

The advantage of this approach is that the overhead on the runtime is kept to a minimum. It is highly dependent on the implementation, but in the example of the JVM, the JFR only has a claimed overhead of about 1% [79].

The downside is that the fidelity of the recordings is highly dependent on the sampling rate. The lower the sampling rate, the more likely it just misses certain events (e.g., method invocations), which leads to the situation that there is no certainty how much it actually recorded — yet, this is true for every *sampling-based* approach and an inherent problem of them. However, the higher the sampling rate gets, the higher is the overhead for recording gets, while still not eliminating said inherent problem.

5.2.2 Instrumentation-based approach

Compared to the *sampling-based* approach described above, an *instrumentation-based* approach can reach complete coverage of theoretically every event happening during the runtime. We are only concerned with method invocations; thus, an *instrumentation-based* approach, in that case, encompasses logging every single method entry together with which method invoked it.

The disadvantage of this approach is that the impact on the runtime performance is immense since every single method invocation is logged.

Generally, there are multiple ways to implement *instrumentation-based* profiling. However, the most common way is some form of aspect-oriented programming (AOP) [37].

The idea of AOP is to inject extra functionality for *cross-cutting concerns*, which describe operations that are not necessarily limited to a particular feature, such as logging [37]. The idea itself is simple; however, first, the user defines *cutting points*, which behave like patterns that are being matched on the source code, for instance: *at every method entry*. They define where in the codebase the extra functionality should be injected. In the next step, the user defines source code that is then injected at every *cutting point* either in a static way at compile time or, in the case of bytecode-based languages, in the moment the bytecode is loaded into the runtime environment [37]. At runtime, at every *cutting point*, method entries in our case, the injected piece of logging code is executed just like the rest of the code [37].

5.3 Semantic coupling extraction

Similarly to the *static coupling* again, the *semantic coupling* extraction only needs the source code itself. Importantly, human-readable, not yet compiled source code is necessary as the semantics are lost in compiled code since it does not contain natural language anymore. We implemented an approach from scratch that conducts the steps regarding the semantic similarity calculation from Subsection 2.2.3:

1. Tokenization
2. Stop word filtering
3. Normalization
4. Vectorization
5. Relevance weighting via *tf-idf*
6. Latent semantic indexing (LSI)

As detailed in subsection 2.2.3, specifically the first two steps are different when analyzing source code compared to traditional natural language.

5.3.1 Natural language processing on source code

Just as the other input dimensions, we implemented our devised methodology on the example of Java applications, hence this subsection will focus on Java source code. Other rules would apply to other languages, although the general concept remains the same.

Regarding the first step, the *tokenization*, an important difference to the *tokenization* of truly natural language is encountered. Because line breaks are an important tool of syntactic separation in programming, they are treated separately. This becomes apparent with an example. Java source code, as well as many other higher-level programming languages, have the notion of recursive packages and importing them or parts of them into the source code of other packages. Consequently, source code, such as the following example 5.1, would include package paths in the term list of the respective document, which would distort the result of the *semantic coupling* analysis. Thus, every line is parsed separately, and language-specific keywords such as `package` or `import` trigger that the line gets discarded.

```
package codes.jakob.semanticcoupling.parsing

import codes.jakob.semanticcoupling.normalization.Lemmatizer
import codes.jakob.semanticcoupling.normalization.Normalizer
import codes.jakob.semanticcoupling.normalization.Stemmer
```

Listing 5.1: Packages and imports in Java

Next, every line of the source code is stripped of non-word characters (i.e., W from regular expressions), which is every character but a-z, A-Z, 0-9, and the underscore character [34]. Before that step, explicit strings (i.e., text in double-quotes) are separately saved, so they do not lose their meaning when stripping the double-quotes. Explicit strings, as well as every other text that is still left then and matches a camel-case pattern is split into a new term at every *camel hump*. Moreover, numeric characters, as well as single characters, are filtered out, as both provide no relevant semantic meaning.

As part of the second step, the *stop word filtering*, a list with stop words specific to the Java language is used to filter out terms that are contained in the list. The list was crafted by us in line with the official Java language specification [88]. Examples for terms that are classified as stop words include:

- class
- public
- static
- void

Finally, everything that was not filtered out until this point is split at white space characters (i.e., t from regular expressions) [34]. Every resulting term is converted to lower case so that the subsequent steps handle the same term in different cases as semantically indifferent.

The remaining steps are conducted just as described in subsection 2.2.3 since, after the second step, the following steps work on term lists as part of documents of the corpus $t_i \in d_i, d_i \in C$, which, at that point, are containing regular natural language.

5.4 Evolutionary coupling extraction

The last input dimension, the *evolutionary coupling*, needs different input. Instead of the application code itself, a log file generated by the utilized version control system (VCS) is required. This mandates that a VCS is used during the development of the input application.

5.4.1 Mining version control system data

The approach leveraged to mine VCS data is modeled after the methodology of Tornhill [64], which is exhibited in subsection 2.2.4.

Theoretically, every VCS that has the notion of revisions that include files and that is able to generate a log file which details past revisions together with the files involved, can be used to extract *evolutionary coupling* information. Common VCS

that we also support as part of our implemented methodology detailed in Chapter 8 are:

- *Git*
- *Subversion*
- *Mercurial*
- *Perforce*
- *Team Foundation Server*

All of the above also support to only generate a partial log for a certain time period. However, *Perforce* and *Team Foundation Server* only support to log the last n revisions compared to a time-based range [89, 84].

A caveat with this approach is that by default, the log files will only include files. Owing to the fact that in applications written in Java, one file is also equivalent to one class, we can generate the coupling graph without any changes to the log format. Nevertheless, it would be possible to extend the *evolutionary coupling* information extraction to support languages that might keep multiple *units* (i.e., the vertices in the graph) in the same file by generating more detailed log files on a line-level within the files. However, this is not covered by our work as we focus on Java applications for our initial implementation.

After parsing the input log file, differing based on the utilized VCS, the process described in Subsection 2.2.4 generates the weighted *evolutionary coupling* graph with the same structure as the other ones such that the vertices $v_i \in V$ are the classes extracted from the VCS log file while the edges $e_i \in E$ are resembling that two classes have overlapping software development life cycles. The weight of the edges is a percentage that indicates how much the life cycles overlap $W(e_i) \in [0.0, 1.0]$. Because two classes can have different *evolutionary coupling* values depending on which direction is calculated, as seen in Figure 5.1, we take the average of these two values if this is the case.

Finally, as discussed in Subsection 2.2.4, we use a threshold for this extraction step to filter out noise. The values are constants that can be changed while the defaults that we employ are:

- Minimum shared revisions between entities: 1
- Time period $[t_1, t_2]$: Every day from [00 : 00, 23 : 59]

For clarification, Figure 5.1 depicts an example timeline to show how the *evolutionary coupling* is calculated via a given VCS log while the direction of the coupling relationship is taken that was extracted out of the static analysis into a directed graph.

Figure 5.1: An example timeline of a VCS log

A textual VCS log is mined for *evolutionary coupling* information by analyzing how many percent of the shared revisions of two entities do overlap. The figure specifically depicts the usage of time ranges and thresholds to obtain sound data. The solid lines are depicting revisions. The dotted lines are depicting midnight in between two days on the timeline. In the example, according to our explanation in 5.4, the *evolutionary coupling* values would be as follows (the values are rounded down):

From \ To	A	B	C
A	-	0.55	0.50
B	0.83	-	0.87
C	0.66	0.77	-

Chapter 6

Creating microservice recommendations

6.1 Representing software as weighted graphs

Our methodology works by clustering a weighted graph; hence we need to construct it first. As discussed in Chapter 4, four general coupling types were chosen to be leveraged for devising the microservice candidates' recommendations. Precisely, the input monolithic application gets analyzed from the view of each of these coupling types, called dimensions from now on.

Out of each of the input dimensions, a weighted graph is constructed with the classes as the vertices $v_i \in V$ and the coupling values between the classes as the weighted edges $e_i \in E$ representing a percentage $W(e_i) \in [0.0, 1.0]$ — resulting in a weighted graph $G = (V, E)$. Consequently, we receive four separate weighted graphs with the different input dimensions as the edge weights.

However, the other extraction methods (i.e., dimensions) covered in the sections below entail one problem that would discredit our whole methodology — they oftentimes do not cover the entirety of the input monolithic application in regard to featuring every class of it as vertices in the resulting weighted graph. As a consequence, it is possible that all four weighted graphs constructed out of the four coupling types are not complete in the sense that they cover the entirety of the input application. As this would defeat the purpose of our approach, an additional static call graph is constructed to be sure that the final graph covers the whole application.

6.2 Merging input dimensional graphs

Four graphs are constructed out of the four input dimensions that need to be merged into a combined one so that it can be clustered eventually. Primarily, this encompasses

a two-step process with the first being a set-theoretic union of the two first graph tuples $G_i = (V, E)$ such that:

$$G_{combined} = G_{static} \cup G_{dynamic}$$

Importantly, this step utilizes a union owing to the fact that the first two input dimensions have downsides in producing a graph that covers the whole application. Nevertheless, they complement each other since they cover separate important aspects of detecting the distinct types of coupling.

Static program analysis has the shortcoming that certain aspects of a written application are only known at runtime, such as the usage of *reflection* [42]. On the other hand, dynamic program analysis entails the problem that it is by no means guaranteed that every class of the executed application is called or even instantiated — the resulting graph is highly dependent on the workload during the dynamic analysis.

In the second step, the two remaining input dimensional graphs are merged into the combined graph $G_{combined}$:

$$G_{combined} = G_{combined} \cap G_{semantic} \cap G_{evolutionary}$$

As part of this step, set-theoretic intersections are used instead as the combined graph resulting out of the merger of the static and the dynamic program analysis acts as a single source of truth — classes that are not connected in there are not able to instantiate or invoke each other in the given application hence intersections are utilized to keep this single source of truth. Precisely, regarding the *semantic coupling* graph, the semantic similarity can be calculated for any two given classes regardless of their connection in the input application codebase.

Consequently, unions ensure that the entirety of the given monolithic application is covered as part of the graph-theoretic representation while intersections add more information to the existing combined graph. Precisely, all vertices from the first two graphs are added to the combined one:

$$V_{combined} = V_{static} \cup V_{dynamic}$$

For the edges, the merging is twofold. The edges themselves are only getting sourced from the first two input graphs to connect the vertices $V_{combined}$ while the other two input graphs do not add new edges but just enrich the information of existing ones:

$$E_{combined} = E_{static} \cup E_{dynamic} \cap E_{semantic} \cap E_{evolutionary}$$

However, the edge weights should not just be added up as all of them resemble percentages. Instead, we use a modifiable *edge weighting formula* which is defining factors for each input dimension to increase or decrease its importance in calculating the combined weight of each edge $\forall e_i \in E_{combined}$ in the combined graph $G_{combined}$:

$$W_{combined}(w_{fstatic}, w_{fdynamic}, w_{fsemantic}, w_{fevolutionary}) = \frac{w_{fstatic} \times W(e_{static}) + w_{fdynamic} \times W(e_{dynamic}) + w_{fsemantic} \times W(e_{semantic}) + w_{fevolutionary} \times W(e_{evolutionary})}{w_{fstatic} + w_{fdynamic} + w_{fsemantic} + w_{fevolutionary}}$$

In the above formula, the weight factors w_x can then be substituted with custom factors. Our default setting is an average with all the weight factors being 1.

Once the combined graph $G_{combined}$ has been constructed, the next step is to apply graph clustering to it such that groups of vertices that have strong coupling, resembled by the combined edge weights $W_{combined}(w_{f_{static}}, w_{f_{dynamic}}, w_{f_{semantic}}, w_{f_{evolutionary}})$ in between them, are more likely to end up in the same cluster. These clusters would then mirror the notion of the *bounded contexts*, introduced in subsection 4.1.2. Thus, each cluster then resembles one microservice candidate recommendation.

Consequently, the question arises which approach to take in clustering the constructed graph $G_{combined}$ at hand, respectively, which graph clustering algorithm to choose, to devise the recommendations as optimally as possible.

6.3 Survey of graph clustering algorithms

The idea of graph clustering was exhibited in the *Background* chapter together with a range of available, renowned algorithms. A variety of graph clustering algorithms exists with a variety of different goals, mechanisms, and features [41, 23, 11]. Consequently, a dozen renowned graph clustering algorithms out of the above sources were evaluated and assessed regarding their usability for our work. A total of nine renowned graph clustering algorithms were chosen and classified in table 6.1; the others had no available reference implementation. The way that classifications are negated was chosen so that \oplus is a positive feature regarding the utilization as part of our work.

Eventually, apart from the *Girvan-Newman* algorithm, the first seven respectively, seven algorithms from table 6.1 were selected to be utilized as part of our work. We chose not to select *Girvan-Newman* as well despite its positive evaluation as Newman designed an improved version of it shortly after together with Clauset and Moore [9]. The other two remaining algorithms had severe downsides that made them unusable as part of our methodology (i.e., not offering a hard clustering, respectively, not working on weighted graphs). The selected graph clustering algorithms are discussed in more detail in the *Background* subsection regarding *Renowned graph clustering algorithms*. The citation numbers in the table are also referenced there.

The characteristics chosen for the survey are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Runtime complexity The runtime complexity of a graph clustering algorithm is not overly significant for our methodology and does not eliminate a given algorithm; nevertheless, it is interesting to include this metric in the conducted survey.

Implementation available This characteristic is the first rated one as it is the most important for our methodology in the sense that the utilization of an algorithm as part of the implementation of our methodology is only possible when an implementation of that algorithm is available.

Does not require number of clusters For our devised methodology, it is beneficial if the utilized graph clustering algorithm does not require a desired number of clusters a priori owing to the fact that this number can only be estimated at best by a software engineer using our implementation. Nevertheless, some algorithms, and more importantly, even some of the selected ones, require said number of clusters as an input parameter. To circumvent this problem, we came up with the solution to execute the affected algorithms multiple times with the same input and differing cluster amounts for a fixed number of iterations. Afterward, the run that produced the highest-scoring metric is selected in place where other algorithms that are not affected would have yielded only one output in the first place. This may sound like a very ineffective solution, but since a single run of any graph clustering algorithm is wholly isolated from another one, this process can be executed concurrently with ease. How exactly this is implemented is discussed in chapter 8.

Deterministic A non-deterministic graph clustering algorithm might produce different results throughout multiple executions. This effect is not a desired characteristic regarding our devised methodology, but it can be mitigated with the solution discussed in the previous paragraph again.

Considers weighted edges This characteristic is of great importance for us since the input graphs will always be weighted. The whole idea of our methodology is to cluster similar vertices where the similarity is resembled via edge weights.

Hard clustering The term *hard clustering* describes that the output clustering of a given graph clustering algorithm assigns one and only one cluster to each vertex of the graph. Comparatively, *soft clustering* or *fuzzy clustering* can assign a vertex to multiple clusters which produces overlapping clusters [41]. Similarly to the previous characteristic, this is not desired regarding our devised methodology as every vertex can only belong to one microservice, which requires *hard clustering* (i.e., partitioning).

Hierarchical The last characteristic is not directly crucial for our methodology as we are only interested in the final output of the clusters as partitions. Nevertheless, as discussed in Section 11.3, this property of graph clustering algorithms could be leveraged for future features.

The reason that the first seven from table 6.1 were selected is that precisely the characteristics *Considers weighted edges* and *Hard clustering* are mandatory for our devised methodology to function.

6.4 Clustering the combined weighted graph

Regardless of which of the first nine graph clustering algorithms out of table 6.1 is chosen, the input and output are the same at their core. Although the exact input and output formats differ between the algorithms, it always boils down to passing a list of edges to the algorithm — listing 6.1 depicts this kind of input format. In this example input, the format follows a tuple of three items (i.e., a triple), namely a vertex, another vertex it is connected to, and the edge weight of the edge connecting them:

$$I_i = (v_1, v_2, W(e_{(1,2)}))$$

such that $v_1, v_2 \in V$, $e_{(1,2)} \in E$, $G = (V, E)$ while $e_{(1,2)}$ is the edge connecting the vertices v_1 and v_2 .

```
1 2 0.50
4 5 0.11
5 6 0.55
6 5 0.60
3 2 0.19
```

Listing 6.1: Example graph clustering algorithm input

In this format, the entire input graph is serialized, while each line resembles a single edge. The integers used for the vertices are their identifiers, some algorithms require identifiers from $[1, n] \in \mathbb{Z}$ where n is the number of edges, others also work with arbitrary strings as identifiers. This fact is discussed in more detail in Chapter 8.

As mentioned in Section 2.3, many graph clustering algorithms discard directions in the input graph, which is no problem for our methodology as the resulting microservice candidate recommendations are finally unidirectional in any case.

After serializing the input graph, the chosen algorithm clusters the graph and returns the clustering as its output. The inner workings of the chosen algorithm are assumed as a black-box function at this point since this was already discussed in Subsection 2.3.1 and as it is not essential for the understanding of this section.

Similarly to the input, the output of the selected algorithms also shares a common notion regarding the format. This example output format is depicted in listing 6.2. In contrast to the input format, the output contains vertices compared to edges and the cluster identifier of each vertex compared to edge weights, as pairs this time:

$$O_i = (v_i, c_i)$$

such that $v_i \in V$, $G = (V, E)$ while $c_i \in C$ resembles the cluster that was assigned to the respective vertex by the graph clustering algorithm. The cluster identifiers commonly range from $[1, n] \in \mathbb{Z}$ where n is the number of clusters. Moreover, they can be duplicated, which signifies that vertices were put into the same cluster.

```
1 1
2 1
3 1
4 2
5 3
6 3
```

Listing 6.2: Example graph clustering algorithm output

Finally, we deserialize the output into a Java object so it can be used to calculate metrics and render the clustered weighted graph for the user.

Citations	Runtime complexity	Implementation available	Does not require number of clusters	Deterministic	Considers weighted edges	Hard clustering	Hierarchical
[28]	$\mathcal{O}(n^3)$	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕
[66]	$\mathcal{O}(nk^2)$	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖
[55]	$\mathcal{O}(mn)$	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊖
[9]	$\mathcal{O}(md \log n)$	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕
[4]	$\mathcal{O}(n)$	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕
[58]	$\mathcal{O}(n)$	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊖
[62]	$\mathcal{O}(n)$	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕
[3]	$\mathcal{O}(n)$	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊖
[60]	$\mathcal{O}(n)$	⊕	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊖	⊖
[15]	N/A	⊕	⊖	N/A	⊖	⊕	⊕

Table 6.1: Graph clustering algorithm survey matrix

All of the information necessary for the classification including the runtime complexity indications are taken out of the original papers of the authors which leads to the fact that some information is unknown as the authors did not calculate or disclose this information. The signs that are used in the matrix correspond to the following meaning:

- ⊕: The statement of the respective cell is *true*
- ⊖: The statement of the respective cell is *false*
- N/A: The statement of the respective cell is *not available*

The way that classifications are negated was chosen so that ⊕ is a positive feature regarding the utilization as part of our work.

- n = number of vertices
- m = number of edges
- k = threshold for the number of resources allocated per vertex
- d = depth of the resulting dendrogram

Chapter 7

Calculating metrics on microservice recommendations

As laid out in Chapter 4, we aimed for an objective mapping of the input monolithic application to its graph-theoretic representation and the clustered output, respectively. Thus, it was necessary for us to also devise objective metrics, numeric in nature, to be able to evaluate the results of our methodology and to answer *RQ2*.

In total, we devised a total of 18 metrics that can be sorted into three sets — some of them being more general and overarching while others are more specific to the problem at hand by offering a direct order of magnitude regarding the quality of the produced output. Some of these metrics are adapted out of literature, others are defined by ourselves. This is indicated in the explanation of each metric below. The three sets of metrics are covered in the following sections while the devised metrics are the following:

- Dynamic analysis input fidelity
- Semantic analysis input fidelity
- Evolutionary analysis input fidelity
- Amount of clusters
- Amount of inter-cluster edges
- Ratio of inter-cluster edge weight
- Mean cluster size
- Static Mean Cluster Factor
- Dynamic Mean Cluster Factor

- Semantic Mean Cluster Factor
- Evolutionary Mean Cluster Factor
- Average Mean Cluster Factor
- Total Mean Cluster Factor
- Static Coupling Modularity
- Dynamic Coupling Modularity
- Semantic Coupling Modularity
- Evolutionary Coupling Modularity
- Average Coupling Modularity
- Total Coupling Modularity

7.1 Input fidelity

The first set of metrics is not directly answering RQ2 but is interesting to look at nevertheless as the *input fidelity* bears implications regarding the eventual quality of the clustering. The term *input fidelity*, that we defined, describes how many percent of the classes of the entire application a given input covers which gives us three different *input fidelity* metrics:

- Dynamic analysis input fidelity
- Semantic analysis input fidelity
- Evolutionary analysis input fidelity

Precisely, this measures how many percent of the edges of a certain input graph are also part of the combined graph $G_{combined}$ covered in chapter 6.1:

$$IF(G_{input}, G_{combined}) = \frac{|E(G_{input})|}{|E(G_{combined})|}$$

The higher this percentage is, the better as it increases the confidence that the results are actually resembling the quality that was calculated for them. Comparatively, if all of the inputs have low *input fidelities*, our methodology still produces output, but the confidence that it is any good is low.

There is no threshold of the *input fidelity* being too low. We instead devised it as a supporting measurement to corroborate the outputs of our methodology. The three input dimensions have different considerations in regard to achieving a high *input fidelity* value.

Dynamic coupling The *dynamic coupling* has the main problem that the *input fidelity* is highly dependent on the workload that was executed during runtime when the dynamic program analysis was conducted. Ideally, every edge of the combined graph should also be part of the *dynamic coupling* graph as it can be theoretically executed, however in reality, this is not often the case. Correctly when utilizing a *sampling-based* profiler, as discussed in section 5.2, the likelihood of reaching 100% *input fidelity* is very low — and even with an *instrumentation-based* profiler, every single possible branch of the program at hand needs to be executed during the recording which is unlikely with non-synthetic workloads which are preferred since the generated microservice candidate recommendations should not be based on synthetic workloads as they would skew the results.

Semantic coupling On the other hand, the *semantic coupling* graphs should reach an *input fidelity* of 100% since a percentage of how semantically similar two classes in a codebase are can always be calculated, even if they are not similar at all, 0% similarity will still count toward the *input fidelity*.

Evolutionary coupling Similarly to the *dynamic coupling*, the *evolutionary coupling* graphs are nearly never reaching full *input fidelity*. The *evolutionary coupling* graph is affected by the threshold used to filter out noise that was introduced in subsection 2.2.4. These thresholds will lead to certain edges not being part of the *evolutionary coupling* graph which will lower the *input fidelity* as a result.

7.2 General clustering quality

The second set of metrics was likewise defined solely by us, it now answers RQ2 but was given its own set because for all four metrics in this set; it can not be strictly defined if low values are better or worse. This reason becomes apparent when looking at the actual metrics:

- Amount of clusters
- Amount of inter-cluster edges
- Ratio of inter-cluster edge weight
- Mean cluster size

Amount of clusters For instance, for the first one in this set, it cannot be said that lower or higher values are better or worse. With the *amount of clusters*, $|C|$ one wants a value in the middle without knowing where the middle exactly lies — more clusters convert to more microservice candidate recommendations which are not necessarily

better. Nevertheless, in this case, the metric offers valuable insights regarding the question of granularity of the produced output.

Amount of inter-cluster edges This metric is calculated by counting the amount of edges in the combined graph $G_{combined}$ that are in between vertices that do not belong to the same cluster:

$$|E_{inter}(G_{combined})| = |\{e_i(v_j, v_k) \in E(G_{combined}) \mid C(v_j) \neq C(v_k)\}|$$

Hence, this metric is a combination of the *Afferent Coupling* and *Efferent Coupling* metrics by Martin [48]. The smaller this value is the less external interfaces the microservice candidate recommendations will have thus it is generally preferred for this metric to be low however it is not desirable to achieve the lowest as possible as this might sacrifice other metrics such as the *Coupling Modularity*.

Ratio of inter-cluster edge weight Similarly to the previous metric, this metric measures how many percent of the total accumulated edge weight lies in between clusters:

$$RW_{inter}(G_{combined}) = \frac{\sum_{e_j \in E_{inter}(G_{combined})} W(e_j)}{\sum_{e_k \in E(G_{combined})} W(e_k)}$$

The rationale here is the same as for the *amount of inter-cluster edges*.

Mean cluster size Regarding the last metric of the second set, it is important to know that as part of the implementation of our methodology detailed in Chapter 8, the size in bytes is calculated for every class of the input monolithic application during the initial analysis step. In the case of Java applications, the compiled JVM byte-code is used for this calculation as it is more standardized and misses arbitrary characters such as line breaks. For other languages or platforms, the source code might be a feasible option after being normalized (e.g., stripped off line breaks). Thus, a way to calculate the accumulated size of a cluster is required beforehand:

$$S(c) = \sum_{v_i \in V(c)} S(v_i)$$

This metric calculates the population mean size overall of the generated clusters:

$$\mu_{S(c)} = \mu(\{c_i \in C \mid S(c_i)\})$$

This gives an insight regarding the size of the clustering which, similarly to the *amount of clusters* metric, depicts the notion of granularity.

7.3 Modularity metrics

Finally, the third set of devised metrics is the most interesting one since, compared to the second set, it answers not only RQ2 but also directly measures the quality of the resulting clustering. In contrast to the second set, for the third set it always holds that higher values are better.

Cluster Factor There are no metrics directly measuring the modularity of a microservice decomposition. Thus, we looked into related domains and found a certain paper over and over again in the reference lists of others [47, 56, 65, 35]: The *Modularization Quality* (MQ) metric was devised by Mitchell and Mancoridis [51] in a paper that researched a very similar idea to ours — instead of clustering classes to achieve a microservice decomposition, they cluster classes of a given application to construct a top-level package structure for it. Additionally, Mitchell and Mancoridis validated their metric in their work [51]. Consequently, this metric is perfectly suited for our methodology as its goal is aligned with ours:

"MQ determines the quality of a partition quantitatively as the trade-off between interconnectivity (i.e., dependencies between the modules of two distinct subsystems) and intraconnectivity (i.e., dependencies between the modules of the same subsystem). This trade-off is based on the assumption that well-designed software systems are organized into cohesive subsystems that are loosely interconnected. Hence, MQ is designed to reward the creation of highly cohesive clusters that are not coupled excessively." [51]

The first step is to calculate *Cluster Factor* (CF) values for every cluster that range on a scale of $[0.0, 1.0]$, as explained in section 2.3. As the last step of calculating the *Modularization Quality* metric, the original paper claims to sum up the *Cluster Factor* values of every cluster. At the same time, this makes no sense when comparing the performance of different graph clustering algorithms as the metric generally grows with rising numbers of clusters hence favoring algorithms that produce higher cluster amounts. Consequently, we decided to instead take the arithmetic mean of all of the *Cluster Factor* values while the ones that yield ∞ due to division-by-zero are treated as 0.0 as the original paper did as well [51]. In this way, the final metric value ranges on the scale of $[0.0, 1.0]$ again instead of having no scale. We propose the name *Mean Cluster Factor* (mCF) for this metric.

Network Modularity The other important metric in this category is the *Network Modularity* Q , which was discussed in greater detail in Section 2.3. We use the exact formula that Newman devised in 2004 under the name *Coupling Modularity* [52].

Adapted modularity metrics Thus, as this set of metrics consists of ten metrics based on the and *Mean Cluster Factor* and *Modularity* metrics, introduced in section 2.3:

- Static Mean Cluster Factor
- Dynamic Mean Cluster Factor
- Semantic Mean Cluster Factor
- Evolutionary Mean Cluster Factor
- Average Mean Cluster Factor
- Total Mean Cluster Factor
- Static Coupling Modularity
- Dynamic Coupling Modularity
- Semantic Coupling Modularity
- Evolutionary Coupling Modularity
- Average Coupling Modularity
- Total Coupling Modularity

Both kinds of metrics are specifically interesting when combined, as high scores in both are a sign of a good partition and graph clustering algorithm in general. Precisely, the first four of each kind of the above share the same underlying equation of calculating the *Mean Cluster Factor* or *Modularity* of their respective coupling graph (e.g., $G_{semantic}$). The *Average Mean Cluster Factor* and the *Average Coupling Modularity* are the arithmetic means of the set of the first four metrics of their kind. Lastly, the *Total Mean Cluster Factor* and *Total Coupling Modularity* are the calculations performed on the combined graph $G_{combined}$.

Accurately, this last set is directly answering *RQ2* by offering numeric and objective metrics that can directly be translated into how qualitative the generated microservice candidate recommendations are.

Chapter 8

Steinmetz: A proof-of-concept implementation

In the last chapters, we described the methodology that we devised to answer *RQ1* as well as the metrics we created to answer *RQ2* — both of these were so far theoretic. However, since the subject of our work is very applied and close to the industry in practice, on top of the theoretic description, we additionally designed and build a fully-functional implementation of our devised methodology.

Our implementation carries the name *Steinmetz* which is the German word for *stonemason*. The name was chosen as our application is used to cut one large stone, the monolith, into many smaller stones, the microservices. Additionally, we published our implementation as open-source software, licensed under the *Apache License v2* ¹ — the entire source code can be found on GitHub ².

The three parts of the application are all bundled into *Docker* containers via *Docker Compose* which allows for easy boot-up and tear-down without installing any dependencies on the operation system apart from *Docker* and *Docker Compose* themselves [72, 71] — a big advantage when putting our implementation to use.

8.1 Architecture

The general, high-level architecture of our application is a three-tier web-based design. The three tiers are namely the front-end, the back-end, as well as the database.

The front-end is built as a *single page application* (SPA), running in a web browser. It is just consisting of static HTML, CSS, and JS files that are purely being interpreted and executed by the web browser.

¹<https://github.com/loehnertz/Steinmetz/blob/develop/LICENSE>

²<https://github.com/loehnertz/Steinmetz/>

The back-end is written in Kotlin, runs as a server process, and exposes a REST-API that the front-end will use and consume to upload and fetch information.

The database is persisting data that needs to be available even when the back-end shuts down and starts again. However, in our application, the purpose of the database is mainly that to cache data after it has been initially processed, as this needs some time. The data itself can be rebuilt with the same input deterministically and will be rarely modified.

As pointed out, for smaller-scale applications, a monolithic architecture makes sense more often by being more comfortable to implement and maintain. Thus, we designed the back-end of our application in a monolith manner.

The implemented application has two significant functionalities that can be used via RESTful endpoints, which are detailed in section 8.3 and depicted in Figure 8.1. These functionalities are to analyze and persist an input monolithic application as well as clustering and retrieving it again as a separate step.

Figure 8.1: Overview of the architecture of our implementation

The implementation is built as a three-tier web-based architecture consisting of front-end, back-end, and database. In the diagram, the two main functionalities of persisting and clustering input monolithic applications are depicted and divided by the horizontal black line.

8.2 Database

As pointed out at the beginning of this chapter, a three-tier, web-based application architecture was chosen, which incorporates a database for persistent data. Instead of utilizing a traditional, relational database model, for our implementation, the graph-based database model was chosen because the persisted data is entirely graph-based. Thus, graph-based database storage lends itself perfectly to the type of data that we need to persist.

Graph databases are a subset of *NoSQL* databases as they are neither relational nor work with the *Structured Query Language* (SQL) [67]. As Vicknair et al. show in their work *A Comparison of a Graph Database and a Relational Database*, when querying graph-based data via a graph database compared to a relational, SQL-based database management system (DBMS), the duration per query is often drastically lower [67]. Additionally, data modeling in the traditional sense is not even necessary as the generated data can be persisted into the database as-is. Due to these two reasons, especially the latter one, a graph-based DBMS was chosen for our implementation.

Similar to other database models, a multitude of DBMS exist following a graph-based approach. We chose the graph database *Neo4j* for the following two reasons. Firstly, it is by far the most popular and most well-maintained graph, DBMS [91]. Secondly, it is implemented in Java and provides an API library for Java and additionally an *Object Graph Mapper* (OGM) which is a library that can map the graph model into native Java objects with built-in serialization and deserialization just as an *Object Relational Mapper* (ORM) would [85].

8.2.1 Object graph mapper

To utilize the *Neo4j* OGM, written and maintained by the *Neo4j* creators [85], one composes classes for each node and edge type that is used. Within *Neo4j*, these are called *Nodes* and *Relationships* [85]. In the following subsections, the process of building OGM models and utilizing them is exhibited.

Relationships

One has to create a class annotated with `@RelationshipEntity("")`, the annotation itself is part of the OGM library and has to be imported. A class annotated like this can then be used to serialize and deserialize edges of the respective graph. The annotation needs to know what the type of the *Relationship* is. This is a string that is necessary since *Neo4j* persists the edges of the input graph as the mentioned *Relationships*. Precisely, the *Neo4j* creators recommend to use single uppercase third-person singular present tense verbs to describe the type of relation [85]. Thus, "CALLS", "OWNS", "KNOWS" would be good examples. Due to this implementation detail of *Neo4j*, this

information has to be provided when annotating *Relationship* classes. The rest of the created class are just properties, some of which are mandatory, while as many additional ones containing data can be added arbitrarily.

```
@RelationshipEntity(type = CALLS)
class CallsRelationship() {
    @Id
    @GeneratedValue
    var id: Long? = null

    @StartNode
    var caller: Unit

    @EndNode
    var callee: Unit

    @Property
    var staticCouplingScore: Int = 0

    @Property
    var dynamicCouplingScore: Int = 0

    @Property
    var semanticCouplingScore: Int = 0

    @Property
    var evolutionaryCouplingScore: Int = 0
}
```

Listing 8.1: Relationship OGM class

The above code example 8.1 is implemented in Kotlin, as this programming language was used to implement the entire back-end, as discussed earlier in this chapter. The class identifier can be chosen arbitrarily while the class needs to encompass three properties. Namely, these are `@StartNode`, `@EndNode`, and `@Id`. The annotations `@StartNode` and `@EndNode` need to point to a non-nullable instance of a *Node* class as exhibited in the following subsection. As the naming implies, this information is used to link the resulting edge of this *Relationship* class to the two vertices that it connects. The `@Id` annotation is used to have a unique identifier once an object of the class gets instantiated so that the OGM can map the object back to the object in the persistent graph data storage. Either the developer supplies these identifiers from the outside, although it is advised just to leverage the `@GeneratedValue` annotation that will handle all this mapping automatically [85]. When utilizing the OGM library within Kotlin, this property has to be declared to be nullable since the identifier might not be known when creating and subsequently inserting a completely new entity. One can add an arbitrary amount of additional data properties to the class via the `@Property`

annotation since *Neo4j* can persist any data together with any *Relationship*. In our use case, these are the coupling scores discussed in Section 4.2. The entirety of the modeled data is covered at the end of this section in 8.2.2.

Nodes

Similarly to the *Relationships*, the *Nodes* are also created by annotating a class, this time with the `@NodeEntity` annotation. Again, certain properties on the defined class are mandatory while others can be added optionally as seen in code example 8.2.

```
class Unit(  
    var identifier: String,  
    var packageIdentifier: String,  
    var projectName: String,  
    var size: Long  
) {  
    @Id  
    @GeneratedValue  
    override var id: Long? = null  
  
    @Relationship(type = CALLS, direction = INCOMING)  
    var callees: MutableSet<CallsRelationship> = mutableSetOf()  
  
    @Relationship(type = CALLS, direction = OUTGOING)  
    var callers: MutableSet<CallsRelationship> = mutableSetOf()  
}
```

Listing 8.2: Node OGM class

The `@Id` is required once again while the `@Relationship` annotations are not mandatory, nevertheless a node in a given graph usually has outgoing or incoming edges (or unidirectional or undirected ones). Since all relationships in *Neo4j* have to be directional but the graph that is constructed as part of our methodology is undirected, the directions out of the merged, final graph are used. Importantly, during further steps or after retrieval out of *Neo4j*, these directions are ignored via the `.equals()` and `hashCode()` methods of the custom data class representing an edge of a graph. Similarly to *Relationships* in *Neo4j*, every *Node* can optionally carry an arbitrary number of additional data fields which are set via regular class properties in the constructor in example 8.2. The *Nodes* as well as the *Relationships* can have additional methods, these are ignored by the OGM as it just looks for properties.

Persisting and retrieving graph data

A `SessionFactory` that is shipped with the OGM library returns `Session` objects that among others offer the methods:

- `save()`
- `loadAll()`

The first one accepts any class instance annotated with the `@NodeEntity` or `@RelationshipEntity` annotation and persists it into the *Neo4j* database. Additionally, serialization and subsequent mapping of native JVM data types into data types supported by *Neo4j* is completely automatic and handled by the OGM [85] although both can be configured manually if wished. Furthermore, the OGM will recursively persist the data attached to the object passed into the `save()` method (e.g., a *Node* connected to another one via a *Relationship*, all three will be persisted). The second method can in return retrieve already persisted data. Its API allows for ordering, pagination, filtering, and other features [85], although our implementation only makes use of the filtering features, such as `session.loadAll(Unit.class, Filter("projectName", ComparisonOperator.EQUALS, "test"))`. Once again, the deserialization and mapping of the data types is handled by the OGM by passing it a static reference to an annotated OGM entity class.

8.2.2 Data models

The devised data models for our implementation are covered in this subsection. Overall, only one *Relationship* and only two *Nodes* are necessary to model our data as depicted in figures 8.2 and 8.3.

Figure 8.2: Node data models

Two *Node* models are necessary. The first one carries the extracted data while the second one is used to persist the calculated metrics on a per-project basis.

Precisely, the *Metrics Node* persists metrics on a per-project basis as described in Section 7.1 — only the fidelity metrics are persisted in the database owing to the fact that their calculation is resource-intensive thus the result is persisted as it will not change in any case. The *Unit Node* is the main *Node* type of the data model as it encompasses the graph that was constructed out of the input monolithic application

Figure 8.3: Relationships data models

One *Relationship* model is necessary. Its sole usage is to link two *Unit Nodes* together as seen in Figure 8.2.

Figure 8.4: Data models example

This is an example how the *Nodes* and *Relationships* work together.

as exhibited in chapter 5. The *CALLS Relationship* is used to persist which *Unit Nodes* are linked to each other. Figure 8.4 depicts how the modeled *Nodes* and *Relationships* behave while Figure 8.5 depicts a class diagram of the involved classes within the back-end.

Figure 8.5: Class diagram of the classes involved in the data model

Each node and relationship type in *Neo4j* is modeled as a class in the back-end.

8.3 Back-end

As already shown, the entire back-end is implemented in the programming language *Kotlin*, which is a language heavily based on Java that compiles to JVM byte-code while also being completely interoperable with Java code meaning that any existing Java libraries can seamlessly be used within Kotlin source code.

The back-end is built as a web-based application with a RESTful API that offers a couple of endpoints for the front-end to use and consume. The server process is utilizing *Netty* [76] as an embedded server, although the native coroutines of Kotlin are used to spawn a new one for every incoming HTTP request. Coroutines are used within the business logic as well. *Coroutines* are a feature of the Kotlin language, which is a lightweight abstraction on top of threads that enable asynchronous programming [78]. The starting point of said server process is the file *Main.kt* that performs all of the scaffolding and starts up the server back-end.

For the API endpoints, the so-called *resources*, a library called *Ktor*, was utilized, which enables straightforward declaration and configuration of them. The library is built and maintained by the Kotlin creator *JetBrains* [74]. All endpoints accept and

respond via *JSON* as the data exchange format while the library *Jackson* is used to automatically serialize and deserialize JSON data [75].

Going deeper into the back-end from the endpoints, *controllers* are handling the request and instantiate and call the respective parts of the business logic.

A *models* directory holds all the classes that are used as *data classes* as they are called in Kotlin — classes that are not encapsulating any advanced business logic and are instead used to pass data around the application in a structured way. Additionally, some may offer static utility methods specific to their usage or when leveraging a unique data format that needs to be converted from other formats.

Some functionalities are small in size and are used by multiple parts of the business logic; hence have no natural location in the application structure. These *utility* classes are therefore residing in a directory called *utility* in the top-level of the application structure. The top-level structure of the application is depicted in figure 8.6 while a detailed explanation of every implemented class can be found in the wiki of *Steinmetz*³.

Figure 8.6: Top-level back-end structure

The top-level file structure of the back-end with a maximum depth of 3.

³<https://github.com/loehnertz/Steinmetz/wiki>

8.3.1 API resources

Namely, there are five resource endpoints for adding new projects, retrieving them, and to eventually cluster them:

1. GET `"/analysis/"`
2. POST `"/analysis/"`
3. GET `"/analysis/{projectName}"`
4. GET `"/analysis/{projectName}/cluster"`
5. GET `"/analysis/{projectName}/optimize"`

Resource 1

The first resource just responds with a list of names of all the projects that have been analyzed in the past using resource 2.

This feature is used in the front-end as well to provide an auto-completing search bar when entering a project name.

Resource 2

The second resource only accepts POST requests and is solely used to create new projects by uploading the necessary data and extracting the coupling information out of it, as discussed in chapter 5. An overview of the data that resource 2 mandates is depicted in table 8.1. Additionally, table 8.2 exhibits what the binary data fields of table 8.1 have to be in the example case that "JAVA" was chosen as the project-Platform. Finally, we added a feature that allows for one of the three following data fields to be missing during the upload owing to the fact that sometimes it is difficult to supply all three (specifically the `dynamicAnalysisFile`) while the analysis can still be performed albeit with lower quality:

- `dynamicAnalysisFile`
- `semanticAnalysisFile`
- `evolutionaryAnalysisFile`

Resource 3

The third resource, GET `"/analysis/{projectName}"`, is solely used to retrieve a project that was persisted earlier via resource 2. Hence, it only mandates the `projectName` as a string to query *Neo4j* for the respective un-clustered graph.

Name	Data type	Description
projectName	String	A freely choosable identifier for the uploaded data
projectPlatform	Enum {"JAVA"}	The platform of the input monolithic application
vcsSystem	Enum {"GIT", "HG", "SVN", "P4", "TFS"}	The VCS system used during the development of the input monolithic application
basePackageIdentifier	String	The root package identifier that all other packages in the project share; is used to filter out dependencies bundled with the application
staticAnalysisFile	Binary	A binary file containing the data for performing the static analysis
dynamicAnalysisFile	Binary	A binary file containing the data for performing the dynamic analysis
semanticAnalysisFile	Binary	A binary file containing the data for performing the semantic analysis
evolutionaryAnalysisFile	Binary	A binary file containing the data for performing the evolutionary analysis

Table 8.1: Data required by resource 1

The data that resource 1 (POST `"/analysis/"`) mandates to function.

Resource 4

The fourth resource is used to cluster a graph that was persisted earlier using resource 2. This is done in two steps as the computational time of the logic behind resource 2 is a lot higher compared to the duration of the clustering of resource 4. Furthermore, the clustering is usually performed multiple times, leveraging different graph clustering algorithms. Thus, it conserves resources to construct the graph-theoretic representation of the input monolithic application only once and to retrieve it multiple times for every request to resource 4.

Name	File extension	Description
staticAnalysisFile	.zip	A .zip file with uncompiled source code
dynamicAnalysisFile	.jfr / .txt	The .jfr extension stems from the <i>Java Flight Recorder</i> which is a profiler shipped with newer JRE versions that can be enabled to conduct dynamic program analysis; the JRE also offers an API to process recorded .jfr files from within another Java application. Alternatively, a plain text file can be provided with each line resembling one method invocation.
semanticAnalysisFile	.zip	Strictly needs the source code archived as a .zip file as the code written by the programmers is necessary to perform natural language processing.
evolutionaryAnalysisFile	.txt	The format is depending on which vcsPlatform was chosen; a log file of the repository of that platform of the application as a plain text file.

Table 8.2: Description of the binary data required by resource 1

The binary data that resource 1 (POST "/analysis/") mandates to function in the case of the Java platform chosen as the projectPlatform.

Resource 5

The last resource is used to optionally optimize the hyper-parameters of our methodology. This is explained in more detail in Subsection 8.3.2.

8.3.2 Logic controllers

Technically, only one logic controller exists, the `AnalysisController`, that branches out into separate classes that implement the actual logic. Figure 8.7 depicts the

structure of the directories containing the logic. The `AnalysisController` class implements the actual controller for all of the `"/analysis"` resources covered in subsection 8.3.1. From there, the analysis controller package branches out into three sub-packages, which are detailed in the following subsections.

Clustering

This package contains everything necessary to perform the clustering of earlier uploaded projects. As exhibited in section 6.3, seven graph clustering algorithms were implemented by wrapping the reference implementations of their authors in a generic API that is consistent within our implementation for all of the utilized graph clustering algorithms.

Clusterer.kt The `Clusterer` class is the entry point for clustering an input graph using any of the available algorithms. The graph that was retrieved out of *Neo4j* is passed into the `Clusterer` after being cloned owing to the fact that by default, all of the available algorithms will concurrently cluster the selected graph such that all of them would work on the same reference in memory which would cause corruption.

ClusteringAlgorithm.kt This file contains an enum that is used to identify which graph clustering algorithm the `Clusterer` should apply to the input graph.

ClusteringAlgorithmManager.kt This file contains an interface that defines a contract that all of the distinct manager classes for each available graph clustering algorithm should implement — it ensures that the APIs for all of the algorithms stay consistent.

EdgeWeightingFormulaCalculator.kt This file contains a class with static methods that implement the edge weighting which was detailed in section 6.2.

Graph clustering managers and executors Every sub-package for each of the available graph clustering algorithms contains a manager class that implements the `ClusteringAlgorithmManager` interface. In these classes, the actual reference implementation of each algorithm is wrapped. Consequently, the implementations in those classes differ vastly from one to the other. A class diagram has been created to depict the classes involved in this step (see Figure 8.8).

Some of the reference implementations are written in Java, which allows us to integrate them into our implementation directly. However, the majority of them are compiled C or C++ programs that are more difficult to integrate. Initially, we

Figure 8.7: Structure of the packages containing the logic

The top-level file structure of the packages that contain the implemented business logic with a maximum depth of 4.

Figure 8.8: Class diagram of the major classes involved in the clustering step

All of the supported graph clustering algorithms have a class that implements their usage.

leveraged the *Java Native Interface* (JNI), a foreign function invocation interface bundled with the Java platform, that can be used to integrate C, C++, and assembly programs into a Java application [87]. On the downside, the source code of the C and C++ programs has to be modified to utilize the JNI. However, we did not have access to all of the reference implementations as source code; some were only shipped pre-compiled. Moreover, all of the reference implementations in C or C++ are designed as *Command Line Interfaces* (CLI) instead of libraries. As a consequence, in the latest version of *Steinmetz*, we opted to wrap the CLI with the `ProcessBuilder` class of the Java platform [86]. This enables us to call any CLI from within a Java application by invoking a process, piping input into `STDIN`, and parsing the output of the invoked program from the processes `STDOUT`. This might seem error-prone at first sight. However, the CLIs are all well-defined, which makes input and output of them easy to encode and decode. Additionally, we added a lot of validation for the input such that we have not seen an error or malfunction when testing and evaluating our implementation so far. The only downside is that the portability of the Java platform is lowered a bit, as the compiled native programs are platform-specific. Nevertheless, the same problem is present when using JNI.

Furthermore, some graph clustering algorithms mandate multiple runs to yield good results. Thus, an additional executor class is utilized there which contains the actual logic while the manager class wraps the executor class and executes multiple instances of it concurrently, leveraging the *coroutine* feature of the Kotlin programming language.

Extraction

The sub-packages within the package `extraction.coupling` in Figure 8.7 are each implementing one input dimension of the ones highlighted in chapter 5. A class diagram of the involved classes can be seen in Figure 8.9.

Firstly, the sub-package `extraction.graph` contains two classes, `GraphConverter` and `GraphInserter`, which are handling the deserialization of a graph retrieved out

Figure 8.9: Class diagram of the classes involved in the extraction step

Every of the four coupling dimensions gets a class that implements it for a supported platform.

of *Neo4j* utilizing the OGM and the insertion of a newly constructed graph into *Neo4j* respectively.

As pointed out earlier, the extraction strategies differ from platform to platform. Thus, for illustrative purposes, we implemented the entire flow for the *Java* platform. The `Platform.kt` file contains an enum with all of the available platforms — currently only *JAVA*. However, later in this section, we show how our implementation can be easily extended for other platforms as this was a conscious design decision to model the architecture in an extendable manner. This enum is used by the controller to know which classes to instantiate and invoke that then conduct the coupling extraction.

The `AbstractExtractor` and its `ExtractorCompanion` are an abstract class and an interface that all of the extraction classes respectively their static companions implement. *Companions* are a feature of the Kotlin language that allows to create static methods by embedding a singleton object within a class that can, therefore, stay stateless and static [77].

Within each of the mentioned sub-packages, there is an abstract class that implements some general behavior necessary for the respective input dimension (e.g., `AbstractDynamicAnalysisExtractor`). The abstract class itself, however, implements the `AbstractExtractor`. Within each of the sub-packages, there are sub-packages for each platform available in the `Platform` enum. In this chapter, the exact implementation of all of these is not covered as the explanation would be very detailed. Instead, only one type of coupling extraction will be covered for the sake of example. All of the others can be studied via the source code itself or via the documentation. The entire structure of the coupling extraction is depicted in figure 8.10.

JavaSemanticCouplingExtractor.kt For the semantic coupling extraction, we opted to build our own implementation from scratch. According to the process exhibited in 2.2.3, we implemented a completely decoupled library that calculates *semantic similarity* of input code bases. Similarly to the main implementation of our methodology,

the Java platform was implemented for now again; the extendability regarding other platforms, however, is easily possible and encouraged.

The library has the simple name *semantic-coupling* and is available as open-source code on GitHub, licensed under the *MIT license*⁴. Additionally, we plan on releasing it on *Maven Central* after the release of this thesis. The library is completely separate from our methodology and also generic in its implementation.

The main method accepts a list of documents as plain-text strings, the source code files, as well as the programming language that they are written in out of an included public enum. The returned result is a list of tuples with the two source code files that were compared as well as their percentage-based similarity as a floating-point number.

Many options can be set when constructing the public entry class of the library. These include if *stemming* or *lemmatization* should be used if *LSI* should be used, if so, how many *LSI* dimensions should be calculated, and if individual source code files should be excluded to gain some execution speed if the user is not interested in their similarity anyways.

Furthermore, the aforementioned Kotlin *coroutines* are heavily leveraged in the library as many steps of the *semantic similarity* calculation can be run concurrently.

Metrics

This package contains two sub-packages, which each contain classes that implement the calculation of the metrics for the input and the clustering, respectively, as detailed in Chapter 7. The distinct implementations are not covered in more detail as they are very close to the mathematical formulae in Chapter 7.

Hyper-parameter optimization

Similarly to the fact that some graph clustering algorithms are run multiple times concurrently to counteract the fact that they require the number of clusters a priori, we implemented a similar idea for the hyper-parameters of our methodology, namely the coupling type weights.

To keep the runtimes of the optimization acceptable, we opted to use the state-of-the-art genetic algorithm *NSGA-II* [69, 46], as it performed faster than comparative algorithms, such as *ϵ NSGA-II* or *MOEA/D*. The *MOEA Framework* was incorporated into *Steinmetz* to be able to utilize reference implementations of the genetic algorithms [32]. The population size of *NSGA-II* is set to 100 and binary tournament selection with replacements is enabled [32].

⁴<https://github.com/loehnertz/semantic-coupling/>

Figure 8.10: Structure of the packages containing the coupling extraction logic
The file structure of the packages that contain the implemented coupling extraction logic.

In the front-end, the user can select which graph clustering algorithm is utilized for the fitness function of the genetic algorithm. The metric that is the output of the fitness function can be selected from the available ones.

8.3.3 Extending the analysis for a new language

It was a conscious design decision in the engineering of the implementation that its core is agnostic of any programming language or platform that it analyzes. As seen in Figure 8.10, the `extraction.coupling` package contains sub-packages for every coupling dimension and then another sub-package for the platforms that are supported. As described earlier, we exemplarily implemented every step of the analysis of software written in Java, hence the `java` packages in each `platforms` sub-package. To be able to analyze another language or platform, one has to conduct four steps:

1. Implement each abstract extractor class for all of the four coupling dimensions
2. Add the new language or platform to the `extraction.Platform` enum
3. Add the new enum entry to the front-end so it becomes selectable
4. Extend the clauses of the methods in `extraction.graph.GraphInserter`

8.4 Front-end

The front-end is designed and built as a *single page application* (SPA) using *Vue.js*, which is a framework to build reactive SPAs utilizing HTML, CSS, and JS that run in a web browser [92].

It supports and encourages to build the SPA as multiple, reusable components. Thus, the engineer has to design up-front how the planned front-end could be logically divided into components — in this regard, it takes ideas from object orientation as one component can build upon other ones and inherit and augment their functionality.

The framework contains control structures to render components conditionally and to loop over an array data structure while rendering HTML and CSS for every item in said array. Features like these are main arguments for utilizing a SPA framework compared to building the front-end application from scratch with plain HTML, CSS, and JS. Yet, the most essential feature is the built-in reactivity, which is not built into web browsers. Precisely, it puts watchers onto every usage of any state in the SPA and automatically re-renders just the effected HTML node in the DOM on-the-fly, which allows the engineer to build applications that are reacting to state changes on their own rather than via a manually implemented trigger [92].

Every component has a transient state that vanishes upon a page refresh or session reload by default. Each component can send messages, mostly consisting of state updates, to child components that they embed as well as to components higher up in the hierarchy. As a consequence, one entry point component exists that the engineer fills with other components to assemble the SPA.

The data to populate the components state, and therefore the page is usually fetched from an API endpoint of a back-end application; this is no different in our case.

8.4.1 User interface

The user interface (UI) is arranged as a set of cards stacked on top of each other. Either, they display control elements or rendered data. Figure 8.11 is a screenshot of the entire front-end with example input and data. Every card has a clear and distinct border with a shadow to visually separate them from each other. In the following subsection, some of the most important cards are covered in more detail. From top to bottom, the cards fulfill the following tasks:

1. Adding a new project by uploading the analysis files. Additionally, the programming language, as well as the VCS platform of the input monolithic application have to be selected.
2. Retrieving a project that was persisted earlier either as the plain graph or in its clustered form.
3. Selecting a graph clustering algorithm for rendering the visualization below as well as selecting a metric that should be used for evaluating the results. A slider sets how many runs graph clustering algorithms should get that are either non-deterministic or have an additional input parameter that determines the granularity of the resulting clustering. In that case, these algorithms are maximally run as often as the slider specifies in a concurrent manner.
4. Changing the weighting for the four input dimensions. By default, every dimension is weighted the same; however, this can be changed by the user.
5. The rendered graph either plain or clustered; every cluster then depicts one microservice. The connections between the units of the input monolithic application as part of the microservices can be examined. The view can be zoomed seamlessly. Moreover, a completely textual view can alternatively be displayed.
6. A brief overview of general metrics that are not specific to clustering.

7. The metrics that are specific to the clustering and more specifically belonging to the graph clustering algorithm selected above.
8. The same card as the one above for each of the available graph clustering algorithms apart from the selected one.

8.4.2 Visualizing microservice recommendations

After uploading a new project or retrieving an existing one, three views exist for visualizing features of the microservice recommendations for that project. Selecting a graph clustering algorithm in the third tile of the UI has the effect that the resulting clustering of the selected algorithm will be used to render all of the views exhibited in this subsection. Regardless of the selection, all of the available algorithms are executed concurrently, but the selected one will provide the data for rendering the views.

Graph view

The first and most obvious view is the *graph view*. It essentially renders the graph that is already persisted in *Neo4j* with the computed clustering visualized as well. Figure 8.12 shows the *graph view* in detail. The whole view can be zoomed in and out seamlessly by scrolling within the card. We tested the visualization with a 10,000 node, fully-connected graph, which was still functional although rendered with a lower frame rate. The rendering is done via a HTML5 `<canvas>`.

Default mode Precisely, orange hexagons depict a microservice while the classes between different microservices have different randomized colors to visually emphasize them toward each other. The orange lines are intra-cluster connections, while green lines are inter-cluster connections. These have different thicknesses depending on their edge weight, which can be displayed by hovering over the edge. Moreover, the inter-cluster edges have arrowheads depicting in which directions the microservices would invoke each other, which can be seen in detail in Figure 8.13. Finally, every unit of each service has its name printed inside of the node as well as the fully qualified name and the byte size when hovering over it, as seen in figure 8.13.

Detailed mode Another mode of the view exists that will display intra-cluster edges, which allows the user to see how units within a service are connected to each other as well as how they are connected to other services and their units. Moreover, units in a square shape are solely accessed within their own service, while units in a diamond

Project Name Base Package Identifier Java Git

Static Analysis Dynamic Analysis Semantic Analysis Logical Analysis

testing-jpeek-111

Louvain Total Coupling Modularity

Coupling Score = (× Dynamic Coupling Score + × Semantic Coupling Score + × Logical Coupling Score) ÷ 3

Metrics

Dynamic Analysis Fidelity: 28%
 Semantic Analysis Fidelity: 95%
 Logical Analysis Fidelity: 20%

Louvain

Amount Clusters: 12
 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 12
 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 9%

Total Coupling Modularity: 0.65
 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.48
 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.13
 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.65
 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.65

Chinese Whispers	Fast Modularity	MCL	Walktrap	Infomap
Amount Clusters: 12 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 29 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 33%	Amount Clusters: 7 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 20 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 13%	Amount Clusters: 7 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 19 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 12%	Amount Clusters: 6 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 13 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 8%	Amount Clusters: 3 Amount Inter-Cluster Edges: 8 Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights: 5%
Total Coupling Modularity: 0.53 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.45 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.31 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.56 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.47	Total Coupling Modularity: 0.69 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.55 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.25 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.68 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.72	Total Coupling Modularity: 0.69 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.53 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.18 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.68 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.72	Total Coupling Modularity: 0.70 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.51 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.13 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.68 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.73	Total Coupling Modularity: 0.51 Average Coupling Modularity: 0.41 Dynamic Coupling Modularity: 0.26 Semantic Coupling Modularity: 0.49 Logical Coupling Modularity: 0.49

Figure 8.11: User interface of the front-end

The front-end consists of multiple cards stacked on top of each other, each filled with either controls or displaying rendered data.

Figure 8.12: The graph view in the UI of the front-end

The front-end offers a *graph view* of the clustered graph that depicts the computed microservice recommendations.

Figure 8.13: A closeup of a node in the graph view

Every node's name is displayed once zoomed in far enough. Furthermore, when hovering over any node, additional information is displayed.

shape are communicating with units from other microservices. This mode can be seen in Figure 8.14 and is activated by toggling the *Hide Inter-Cluster Edges* option.

Natural mode A last, additional graph view mode renders the graph in a more natural form without artificial changes to the way that the clusters are rendered. This mode is mainly interesting to examine the structure or architecture of the input monolithic application. The mode can be seen in Figure 8.15 and is activated by toggling the *Clustered View* option which also disables the *Hide Inter-Cluster Edges* as well.

Textual view

As large input monolithic applications will also produce large graph clusterings, the readability of the *graph view* is hindered. However, primarily when the microservice recommendations should be implemented, a textual view is preferred as the graphical nature of the *graph view* is expected not to provide enough of an overview regarding the resulting microservice candidate recommendations. This view can be seen in further detail in Figure 8.16.

Figure 8.14: A closeup of the detailed graph view mode

The graph view has a second, more detailed mode that also displays all of the inter-cluster as well as intra-cluster edges.

Figure 8.15: A closeup of the natural graph view mode

The *graph view* has a third mode that can be used to see a more natural rendering of the clustered graph. This can be used to examine the structure of the input monolithic application on its own.

Figure 8.16: A closeup of the textual view

Additionally to the *graph view*, a solely *textual view* was implemented that just displays which units belong to which service.

Metrics view

Lastly, the UI displays an overview of the metrics that we selected. All of those are covered in detail in chapter 7. The big tile on top of the others, as seen in figure 8.17, contains general metrics that are not measuring anything regarding the clustering but rather the input.

Figure 8.17: A closeup of the metrics view

Every available graph clustering algorithm is evaluated while the one that scored the highest in the selected metric is additionally highlighted in green.

The tile directly below is displaying results regarding the selected graph clustering algorithm. However, the information is identical to the smaller tiles below. Each tile corresponds to one of the available algorithms; the selected one just gets the largest tile for better visibility.

Finally, the algorithm that scored the highest in the metric that was selected in the third tile, next to the selected algorithm, is highlighted in green.

Chapter 9

Experiment design

Our full implementation exhibited in Chapter 8 allowed us to evaluate our methodology using actual software, which was selected via the definition of a multitude of criteria followed by extensive research to identify possible candidates for the experiments.

9.1 Experiment setup

Five freely available open-source applications, as well as a closed source one provided by the host organization of this thesis project, were chosen to be run through *Steinmetz* to generate a set of microservice candidate recommendations. The goal is to determine which graph clustering algorithm performed the best in the case of each input application as well as overall.

Additionally, the performance of the PoC that we implemented was analyzed.

9.1.1 Subjects

As shown in Section 2.1, a microservices-based architecture only makes sense for large-scale, web-based, back-end applications compared to libraries, SDKs, and dedicated GUI software. Consequently, software that falls into said category had to be selected, which is far more difficult compared to the other categories as such software is typically found in enterprises and not overly common in the open-source sector.

The selected applications had to be implemented with the Java programming language as the first version of *Steinmetz* that we implemented for now only supports input software that was written in Java.

Furthermore, to be able to analyze all four of the input dimensions covered in section 4.2, the selected applications had to fulfill another, more distinct set of criteria:

- Static coupling: Being available as uncompiled source code

- Dynamic coupling: Executable in the latest version
- Semantic coupling: Being available as uncompiled source code
- Evolutionary coupling: Being version-controlled via a supported VCS

Based on these basic criteria, we conducted an intensive survey of possible ones via the search functionality of GitHub. Precisely, these projects were found via the following query 9.1.

```
NOT library NOT framework NOT android NOT distributed NOT client stars:>500 language:Java
```

Listing 9.1: GitHub experiment subjects search query

We examined projects with at least 500 stars to filter out educational projects that are most likely not peer-reviewed. Sadly, the GitHub search only allows up to five NOT operators. Thus, this query still yields good results overall but still a lot of false positives such as:

- Libraries or SDKs not filtered out by the query
- Chinese repositories with unknown contents
- Collections of example code or interview questions

After discarding these, the first 50 pages of the search results were analyzed for software projects of varying sizes with the following properties:

- standalone
- large-scale
- web-based
- back-end
- monolithic

Finally, the ten applications seen in table 9.1 that fulfill these requirements were selected.

9.1.2 Difficulties

As discussed in the previous section, the selected applications have to fulfill a set of requirements for each of the four input dimensions. Furthermore, the *dynamic coupling* involves another difficulty, which was already discussed in Subsection 2.2.2 — owing to the fact that the software has to be executed in order to conduct *dynamic program analysis*, this input dimension involves a lot more work than any of the others.

Moreover, another problem arises, which is more specific to our use case: The dynamic coupling between units of the application that should later belong to different

microservices only becomes apparent while the application is under full load by a real user base. Otherwise, *dynamic coupling* will be measured while it is easy to see that the results are flawed when not analyzing the actual load on the system.

This problem is twofold. Firstly, the coupling of non-production workload is usually completely different from the workload generated by an actual user base, and secondly, it is unlikely that most parts of the application will even be invoked. One set of metrics that we devised that measure the *fidelity* of the different analysis types is useful to determine how severe this latter problem is. However, the first problem is a dilemma as it just cannot be known how well the workload during the *dynamic analysis* resembled the *dynamic coupling* of the application when not conducted in a production environment.

Although load testing and example workloads exist, the recordings will still not reach the quality of ones recorded in a running production environment. Apart from the fact that even example workloads are very sparse for open-source software, a production environment is simply not available to us to guarantee high quality and high fidelity *dynamic analysis*. Overall, this is specifically problematic as some *dynamic coupling* will always be recorded, which will, in turn, also be used to generate the microservice candidate recommendations, which are ergo flawed and unreliable.

Due to this difficulty and its possible repercussions, we decided to leave the *dynamic coupling* dimension out of most of the experiments. Nevertheless, since our implementation allows for one input dimension to be left out when conducting an analysis, this difficulty could be circumvented in all of the experiments.

Finally, to test that the entirety of our implemented methodology was working as designed, we conducted the first experiment by analyzing one of the projects with all the available dimensions, thus including the *dynamic coupling*. The details of this first, as well as the other experiments, are discussed in more detail in the following Section 9.2.

9.2 Experiment execution

Before the actual experiments are exhibited, the criteria of each experiment are discussed and explained. Table 9.2 shows the five selected criteria that each of the following experiments sets.

9.2.1 Experiment N° 1

For the first experiment, we analyzed only the test subject *Heritrix* with all available dimensions. The reason for this is that due to the nature of *Heritrix*, it is feasible to record real-world workload regarding the *dynamic coupling*. *Heritrix* is a web-crawler, which means that after being given one or multiple seeds, it generates its work

automatically by adding newly found links to a queue. Consequently, no workload has to be synthetically generated or recorded, which means that the problem discussed in subsection 9.1.2 can be circumvented in this way. Eventually, we profiled *Heritrix* during its runtime for 48 hours with the *Java Flight Recorder*, which yielded a recording of 4.5 gigabytes, which was used for this experiment. Importantly, this is a proof of concept experiment as we acknowledge that its results could be more meaningful with a larger set of test subjects. The *coupling dimension weights* were set to different values. These values were set by running the hyper-parameter optimization detailed in 8.3.2 to maximize the *Total Coupling Modularity* metric. Finally, the following criteria were determined:

- Coupling dimensions: static, dynamic, semantic, evolutionary
- Coupling dimension weights: $7 \times \textit{static}$, $7 \times \textit{dynamic}$, $2 \times \textit{semantic}$, $1 \times \textit{evolutionary}$
- Graph clustering algorithms: Chinese Whispers, Clauset-Newman-Moore, Infomap, Label Propagation, Louvain, MCL, Walktrap
- Maximum number of iterations: 100
- Recorded metrics: *Total Mean Cluster Factor*, *Total Coupling Modularity*, *Amount of Clusters*, *Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights*

9.2.2 Experiment N° 2

For the second experiment, we analyzed all of the aforementioned test subjects with our implementation. In essence, the criteria of this experiment are the same as the one of the first one, while the *dynamic coupling* dimension is left out due to the reasons described in Subsection 9.1.2. The goal of this experiment is to determine if the *mCF* or the *Q* metric generally performs better:

- Coupling dimensions: static, semantic, evolutionary
- Coupling dimension weights: $1 \times \textit{static}$, $1 \times \textit{semantic}$, $1 \times \textit{evolutionary}$
- Graph clustering algorithms: Chinese Whispers, Clauset-Newman-Moore, Infomap, Label Propagation, Louvain, MCL, Walktrap
- Maximum number of iterations: 100
- Recorded metrics: *Total Mean Cluster Factor*, *Total Coupling Modularity*

9.2.3 Experiment N° 3

In this third experiment, we recorded the average of each metric per graph clustering algorithm with the intent to detect which ones generally perform overly good or bad:

- Coupling dimensions: static, semantic, evolutionary
- Coupling dimension weights: $1 \times \textit{static}$, $1 \times \textit{semantic}$, $1 \times \textit{evolutionary}$

- Graph clustering algorithms: Chinese Whispers, Clauset-Newman-Moore, Infomap, Label Propagation, Louvain, MCL, Walktrap
- Maximum number of iterations: 100
- Recorded metrics: *Total Mean Cluster Factor* per algorithm, *Total Coupling Modularity* per algorithm, Correlation between *Total Mean Cluster Factor* and *Total Coupling Modularity* per algorithm, *Amount of Clusters* per algorithm, *Ratio Inter-Cluster Edge Weights* per algorithm

9.2.4 Experiment N° 4

In the fourth and hindmost experiment, we approximated the *Pareto frontiers* of each of the inputs regarding the coupling dimension weights as the variables. We maximized the counterparts of the weights in form of the dimensional coupling metrics. Concretely, this means that an optimal solution is one where each of the input-dimensional objectives achieves Pareto-optimality. We defined the input variable search space as floating-numbers in the range $[0.0, 1.0]$ that are then divided by the sum of them to relativize them.

We utilized the *NSGA-II* algorithm by Deb et al. [13]. This algorithm was chosen as studies identified it as one of the state-of-the-art genetic algorithms [69, 46]. Next to other candidate algorithms, such as ϵ *NSGA-II* or *MOEA/D*, *NSGA-II* performed faster regarding our optimization problem, which was of importance to us as clusterings taking up to one minute to converge are not seldom with the input sizes we use. Thus, shorter runtimes were of importance. We set the population size of *NSGA-II* to 100 and enabled binary tournament selection with replacements [32].

We used the inputs that have only recorded static, semantic, and evolutionary dimensions as they are the majority, making our sampling size larger. Thus, our optimization problem is three-dimensional in nature. Nevertheless, we also verified that this experiment works with all four dimensions resulting in a four-dimensional optimization problem.

- Coupling dimensions: static, semantic, evolutionary
- Coupling dimension weights: static, semantic, evolutionary
- Graph clustering algorithms: Clauset-Newman-Moore
- Maximum number of solution evaluations: 10000
- Recorded: *Static Coupling Weight*, *Semantic Coupling Weight*, *Evolutionary Coupling Weight*, *Static Coupling Modularity*, *Semantic Coupling Modularity*, *Evolutionary Coupling Modularity*

Project	SLOC	Commits	Description
Apache OpenMeetings	4,222	2,755	Provides video conferencing, instant messaging, white board, collaborative document editing and more
Apache Solr	203,364	33,018	A high-performance, fully-featured text search engine
BigBlueButton	36,578	26,774	An HTML5-based open-source application that enables teachers to engage and collaborate with their students
Google Bazel	340,747	24,442	A fast, scalable, multi-language and extensible build system
Halo	23,010	1,788	An excellent open source blog publishing application
Heritrix	15,210	2,126	The <i>Internet Archive's</i> open-source, extensible, web-scale, archival-quality web crawler project
KeyCloak	419,351	12,340	Open source identity and access management for modern applications and services
OpenCMS	326,836	23,674	An open source content management system
Openfire	77,112	9,368	An open source XMPP server
OpenTripPlanner	67,976	9,560	An open source multi-modal trip planner
Red5	8,528	481	Red5 is an Open Source Flash Server
Teammates	42,280	17,221	An online tool for managing peer evaluations and other feedback paths of students
Traccar	52,090	6,202	An open source GPS tracking system
XWiki	238,253	38,841	An advanced open source enterprise wiki

Table 9.1: The software projects selected for the evaluation

Criterion	Explanation
Coupling dimensions	The coupling dimensions that were used for the analysis (see Section 4.2)
Coupling dimension weights	The weights that were assigned to each of the utilized dimensions (see Section 6.2)
Graph clustering algorithms	The graph clustering algorithms that were used for the experiment (see Section 2.3)
Maximum number of iterations	The maximum number of iterations used for algorithms that require an input parameter (see Paragraph 6.3)
Recorded metrics	The metrics that were recorded as part of the experiment (see Chapter 7)

Table 9.2: Explanations of the criteria of the experiments

Chapter 10

Experiment results and discussion

10.1 Experiments

In the following four subsections, the results of the four experiments that we conducted are presented and discussed.

10.1.1 Experiment N° 1

The results of experiment N° 1 can be found in Figures 10.1 and 10.2.

Generally, all available graph clustering algorithms perform well, although there is an interesting pattern that the *Dynamic Mean Cluster Factor* is a lot lower than the *Dynamic Coupling Modularity*. We have no explanation for why this happens. However, at least for the *Coupling Modularity* variations, all input dimensions achieve good scores. The *Dynamic Analysis Fidelity* is the lowest, the *Evolutionary Analysis Fidelity* in the midfield, and the *Semantic Analysis Fidelity* is the highest. The *Static Analysis Fidelity* does not exist in the sense of the others since it is always 100% as it is the single source of truth in which classes can reach others.

In both clustering metrics, the *Clauset-Newman-Moore* algorithm performs the best. It also achieves the second-lowest *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)*. The resulting clustering is rendered in Figure 10.2, which also looks reasonable in the visual and textual view.

We can conclude that *Steinmetz* works as expected. It correctly analyzes the four input dimensions, builds a weighted graph out of them, and clusters it with all seven available graph clustering algorithms. This directly answers RQ1 and presents our solution as a working methodology.

Figure 10.2: The highest scoring clustering of the first experiment

This clustering was produced by the *Clauset-Newman-Moore* graph clustering algorithm with a score of 0.94 in the mCF and 0.76 in the Q metric.

10.1.2 Experiment N° 2

The results of experiment N° 2 can be found in Figures 10.3, 10.4, 10.5, 10.6, and 10.7.

It can be deduced from the heatmaps that the *mCF* metric only uses a small range of scores and generally awards high scores. It also reaches a perfect score of 1.0 when only a single cluster is generated, which is not preferable. On the other hand, the range of scores of the *Q* metric is broader and more pronounced. It also awards very low scores to some clusterings. Generally, the two metrics have a positive bivariate correlation of $R = 0.48$ while this is mainly not even higher due to some clusterings that achieve very high scores in the *mCF* metric while having very low scores in the *Q* metric — they can be seen in the lower right-hand corner of figure 10.5. To determine which metric is more wrong for these clusterings, we manually studied said clusterings. Figure 10.8 shows the most extreme of these cases. It can be seen that the clustering just consists of one huge microservice with seven smaller ones directly attached to it. Objectively, this is not a good clustering as it the *micro*-aspect of microservices is not satisfied.

Thus, we can deduct that the *Q* metric is more suitable for assessing the output quality of microservice decomposition methodologies than the *mCF*, which directly answers RQ2. Additionally, as Figures 10.6 and 10.7 depict, the *mCF* metric is more highly correlated with the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)*, a metric that should neither be very high, nor very low. Comparatively, the *Q* metric only shows a weak correlation. A lower *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* makes much sense intuitively as it generally lowers the coupling between microservices. However, it is not desirable to optimize toward the least possible *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* as this generally will lead to a few, huge microservices. Both of the main clustering metrics are negatively correlated to the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)*, while apparently giving an edge over that metric since the correlation is not perfect. There is a valley of data points in the lower left-hand corner of Figure 10.7, for the preferred *Q* metric, that achieves good *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* values while having very low *Q* scores at the same time.

10.1.3 Experiment N° 3

The results of experiment N° 3 can be found in Figures and Tables 10.9, 10.10, 10.11, 10.12, 10.13, and 10.12.

It can be noticed quickly that the *Chinese Whispers* algorithm performs poorly overall. Its performance is far worse than that of any other algorithm. Furthermore, some algorithms perform better or worse on different projects, while the *Chinese Whispers* algorithm is consistently underperforming. In the same vein, the *Chinese Whispers* algorithm stands out with yielding a grotesque amount of clusters, going

Figure 10.3: Heatmap of the mCF metric for each of the input projects per graph clustering algorithm

Figure 10.4: Heatmap of the Q metric for each of the input projects per graph clustering algorithm

Figure 10.5: Bivariate correlation between the *mCF* and the *Q* metric for all results

Figure 10.6: Bivariate correlation between the *mCF* and the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* metric for all results

Figure 10.7: Bivariate correlation between the Q and the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* metric for all results

over the threshold of 1,000, as seen in Figure 10.12. The *Infomap*, *Walktrap*, and *Label Propagation* algorithms are performing not very consistently, achieving both very good as well as terrible results.

On the other hand, it can be observed that the algorithms *Clauset-Newman-Moore* and *Louvain* perform very similarly in all of the three recorded metrics, which is due to the fact that they are both heuristic algorithms optimizing toward the *Modularity* metric 2.3.1. Interestingly, on most occasions, however, the *Louvain* algorithm performs slightly better, which is a confirmation of the fact that it was developed after the *Clauset-Newman-Moore* algorithm and is seen as an improvement upon it by literature [41]. The *MCL* performs somewhere in the middle, but not badly. All of these results can be found in figures 10.9 and 10.10.

Thus, we can deduct that both the *Clauset-Newman-Moore*, as well as the *Louvain* algorithm, are the most suitable for generating microservice recommendations, which directly answers RQ3. This notion can still be supported when looking at the additional Figures 10.11 and 10.13. Both of the best performing algorithms have high bivariate correlations between their scores in the two main clustering metrics with $R = 0.90$ and $R = 0.89$ for *Clauset-Newman-Moore* and *Louvain* respectively. Other algorithms, such as *Chinese Whispers*, also achieve a high correlation of $R = 0.75$, but in this case, both main metrics agree upon that it performs badly. Likewise, the bivariate correlation between the *Total Coupling Modularity* and the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* per algorithm is strongly negatively correlating for the

Figure 10.8: The clustering with the largest difference between the mCF and Q metrics

two best-performing algorithms. This indicates that lower inter-cluster edges weights are resulting in better microservice recommendations, which makes intuitive sense given that ideally, microservices should only be coupled to a minimum to each other. As shown in the subsection on experiment N° 2, some negative correlation in this regard is expected and positive. This can be confirmed by the fact that algorithms that already achieved bad scores in the main clustering metrics even have positive bivariate correlations to the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* which intuitively does not make any sense since more coupling between microservices is never desired.

Finally, there is an interesting insight. The bivariate correlation between the *Total Coupling Modularity* metric and the *Amount of Clusters* is positively correlated for the *Clouset-Newman-Moore* and *Louvain* algorithms, compared to others. Although we have no other sources of information to confirm or deny this, it seems that generally speaking, higher amounts of clusters (i.e., finer microservice granularity) is better. These results can be found in table 10.1.

Figure 10.9: Violin plot of the *mCF* metric over all of the graph clustering algorithms

10.1.4 Experiment N° 4

The results of experiment N° 4 can be found in Figures and Tables 10.14, 10.2, 10.3, 10.4, 10.15, 10.16, 10.5, 10.6, 10.7, 10.17, 10.18, 10.19, and 10.8.

We conducted this last experiment utilizing the *Clouset-Newman-Moore* algorithm as the fitness function, as well as the dimensional *Q* metrics as the metrics to optimize (i.e., the metrics that measure the objectives). These were chosen as the above

Figure 10.10: Violin plot of the Q metric over all of the graph clustering algorithms

Figure 10.11: Bivariate correlation between the *mCF* and the Q metric for all of the graph clustering algorithms

Figure 10.12: Bivariate correlation between the Q metric and the *Amount of Clusters* for all of the graph clustering algorithms

Figure 10.13: Bivariate correlation between the Q metric and the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights (%)* for all of the graph clustering algorithms

Graph Clustering Algorithm	Correlation (R)	Significance (p)
Chinese Whispers	-0.31	0.29
Clauset-Newman-Moore	0.46	0.1
Infomap	0.6	0.02
Label Propagation	0.08	0.78
Louvain	0.51	0.07
MCL	-0.18	0.54
Walktrap	-0.78	0.0

Table 10.1: Bivariate correlations between the *Total Coupling Modularity* and the *Amount of Clusters*

experiments show that this graph clustering algorithm and clustering metric are preferred.

In total, we obtained the *Pareto frontiers* of our 14 inputs. Only the input project *Red5* only always yielded a single solution with exactly the same objective values (seven digits after the decimal point), even when optimized with other genetic algorithms than *NSGA-II* and throughout multiple runs with different seeds. We conclude that this happens due to the small project size of *Red5*, indicating that all the genetic algorithms likely found not only a Pareto-optimal solution but the globally optimal solution to the clustering problem of this input. For all the other 13 inputs, traditional *Pareto frontiers* were generated.

After analyzing the results, we made four major findings:

1. The majority of input projects share a very similar *Pareto frontier* shape.
2. In these same projects, the static and semantic objectives are highly positively correlated. Similarly, the evolutionary objective is negatively correlated to the other two.
3. The majority of the variable combinations are having high evolutionary weight while having lower static and semantic weights.
4. The semantic objective can still achieve high values with an extremely low respective weight variable. The picture is similar, albeit less pronounced, for the static objective. At the same time, the evolutionary objective requires higher weight variable values to achieve Pareto-optimal solutions.

Firstly, the frontiers of all the input projects are very similar in shape. Apart from *Halo*, *Heritrix*, *OpenTripPlanner*, *Traccar*, and *XWiki*, the other eight input projects retain frontiers that look very similar to the example of *KeyCloak*, the largest input, as seen in Figure 10.14. The frontier runs in a half-arc curve that originates from the zero points of the static and semantic objectives, smoothly rising in their values with an increasing steepness of the curve, decreasing the evolutionary objective value at the same time, resulting in a sharp drop at the end. We have no definitive explanation of why this could be as we discovered no measurable correlating attributes that would distinguish these five input projects from the other eight. We can only conclude that their software architectures or commit strategies seem to be different, which shows as well in the following findings.

Figure 10.14: The *Pareto frontier* of the *KeyCloak* input, optimizing the input dimensional *Q* metrics

We can deduct that the static and semantic dimensions are highly positively correlated which is corroborated by their Pearson *R* values, as shown by the top part of table 10.2. Only *Apache Solr* has a significantly decreased correlation while

showing the same frontier shape. At the same time, the same correlations for the other five above-mentioned input projects are significantly lower throughout, as the bottom of table 10.2 depicts. Similarly, the evolutionary objective is negatively correlated toward the static and semantic objective respectively, as the top parts of tables 10.3 and 10.4 show. Interestingly, in this regard, also the five projects that had only a low positive correlation between the static and semantic objectives show a high negative correlation between the evolutionary and static objectives, as seen in bottom part of table 10.3. On the other hand, toward the semantic objective, the evolutionary objective is a lot less highly negatively correlated, as depicted in the bottom of table 10.4. We conclude that this likely happens as the static and semantic dimensions are extracted out of the same input, the source code, while the evolutionary dimension is derived from VCS logs. Additionally, we saw in the initial dataset after generating the separate graphs out of the inputs that the evolutionary input fidelity is usually lower than the semantic one, which might make a resulting clustering less precise in the evolutionary dimension.

Coming to the input variables of our optimization problem, we see that they are very clustered in the search space. Figure 10.15 shows this on the example of the *KeyCloak* input project once again. The picture is very similar again for the other eight input projects that share a *Pareto frontier* shape, as tables 10.5, 10.6, and 10.7 show. The semantic weight variables are almost always very low. The static weight variables are slightly more spread out but also rarely exceed 0.5. The evolutionary weight variables are often seen in higher value ranges. Moreover, as depicted by Figure 10.16, for many input projects, such as *Teammates*, this clustering pattern is even more extreme as the evolutionary weight variables are either very high or very low, which is corroborated by the much higher variance values for these variables.

Interestingly, the semantic objective scores still reach high values even if its weight variable approaches 0.0, as seen in Figure 10.17 on the example of the *KeyCloak* input project again. A similar picture can be observed for the static weight variables, shown in Figure 10.18. It seems to us that the semantic dimension is partly encoded in the static one, which can already be seen in the previous findings as they are highly positively correlated toward each other. For many inputs, one could theoretically leave the semantic input dimension out of the analysis, while still achieving high semantic objective scores. For the eight input projects sharing the *Pareto frontier* shape of a half-arc, the software architectures seem to make the semantic measurement almost obsolete as even with small input weight variables of < 0.2 , high output objective scores can be reached. On the other hand, the evolutionary objective seems to be much more sensitive to its input weight variable, as the comparative Figure 10.19 confirms. This ties together the first three findings, as the static and semantic objectives do not seem to be too sensitive to their respective weight variables while still scoring high values, while also having a lot higher valued evolutionary weight

Figure 10.15: The input variables that lead to the *Pareto frontier* of the *KeyCloak* input, as seen in Figure 10.14

Figure 10.16: The input variables that lead to the *Pareto frontier* of the *Teammates* input

Input Project	Correlation (R)
Apache OpenMeetings	0.70
Apache Solr	0.33
BigBlueButton	0.60
Google Bazel	0.38
KeyCloak	0.83
OpenCMS	0.87
Openfire	0.86
Teammates	0.79
<hr/>	
Halo	0.01
Heritrix	0.30
OpenTripPlanner	0.42
Traccar	0.57
XWiki	0.51

Table 10.2: Bivariate correlations ($p < 0.001$) (*Halo*: $p = 0.33$) between the *Static Coupling Modularity* and the *Semantic Coupling Modularity* objectives for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

variables compared to the other two, which is confirmed by the shape of most of the *Pareto frontiers* that consist of a plateau of high evolutionary objective scores while slowly decreasing in this regard toward higher scores for the other two objectives.

Finally, we decided to look into the question of how the different Pareto-optimal solutions affect the microservice candidate recommendations. To do this, we identified the input project that shows the highest ranges for all the three objective values, which turned out to be *OpenCMS*. The results are shown in table 10.8. Clustering the weight variable combination that leads to the lowest average objective values (i.e., the furthest away from the *knee-point* of the *Pareto frontier*) resulted in a clustering consisting of double the *Amount of Clusters* compared to the highest average solution (i.e., the *knee-point*), while having a third of the *Ratio of Inter-Cluster Edge Weights*. The solution that is the midpoint of the range is interestingly in the middle.

Figure 10.17: The semantic input variables and output objective values that lead to the *Pareto frontier* of the *KeyCloak* input, as seen in Figure 10.14

Figure 10.18: The static input variables and output objective values that lead to the *Pareto frontier* of the *KeyCloak* input, as seen in Figure 10.14

Input Project	Correlation (R)
Apache OpenMeetings	-0.70
Apache Solr	-0.64
BigBlueButton	-0.82
Google Bazel	-0.73
KeyCloak	-0.81
OpenCMS	-0.84
Openfire	-0.85
Teammates	-0.80
Halo	-0.67
Heritrix	-0.85
OpenTripPlanner	-0.81
Traccar	-0.86
XWiki	-0.78

Table 10.3: Bivariate correlations ($p < 0.001$) between the *Evolutionary Coupling Modularity* and the *Static Coupling Modularity* objectives for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

10.2 Performance

The performance results can be found in Figures 10.20, 10.21, 10.22, and 10.23. On purpose, the same scales are used in all of the plots such that the results and the runtime complexity can be compared.

This section presents the results of the performance evaluation of the PoC that we implemented as part of this thesis project. For the runtime, we simply recorded the time each step of the complete analysis took in seconds. Namely, these are the static, semantic, and evolutionary analyses. The first two are compared to the SLOC of the input projects, while the latter is compared to the number of commits. Finally, the total runtime, including the merging of all four graphs and the insertion into the database, was recorded.

The dynamic analysis is not covered in this subsection, as we had only a single

Input Project	Correlation (R)
Apache OpenMeetings	-0.84
Apache Solr	-0.68
BigBlueButton	-0.51
Google Bazel	-0.70
KeyCloak	-0.80
OpenCMS	-0.72
Openfire	-0.86
Teammates	-0.82
<hr/>	
Halo	-0.43
Heritrix	-0.52
OpenTripPlanner	-0.67
Traccar	-0.50
XWiki	-0.38

Table 10.4: Bivariate correlations ($p < 0.001$) between the *Evolutionary Coupling Modularity* and the *Semantic Coupling Modularity* objectives for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

recorded data point. However, for the sake of completeness, the dynamic analysis of the first experiment took 64 seconds for a profiler recording of 4500 megabytes in size. The clustering runtime was not measured as we do not influence it since solely the runtime complexity of each of the graph clustering algorithms determines that.

As Figures 10.21 and 10.22 show, the semantic and evolutionary analysis have a less than linear runtime complexity. The static analysis in 10.20 is what drives the total runtime the most. Nevertheless, the total runtime of the PoC is predictable, with a bivariate correlation between input size and runtime being a very high $R = 0.92$. Due to this, the small confidence interval, and the slope of the regression line, the runtime complexity of the PoC seems to be $\mathcal{O}(N)$, as Figure 10.23 depicts.

Figure 10.19: The evolutionary input variables and output objective values that lead to the *Pareto frontier* of the *KeyCloak* input, as seen in Figure 10.14

Figure 10.20: The PoC performance of the static coupling analysis

All analyzed projects are plotted according to their SLOC and how long the static coupling analysis took respectively.

Figure 10.21: The PoC performance of the semantic coupling analysis

All analyzed projects are plotted according to their SLOC and how long the semantic coupling analysis took respectively.

Figure 10.22: The PoC performance of the evolutionary coupling analysis

All analyzed projects are plotted according to their amount of commits and how long the evolutionary coupling analysis took respectively.

Input Project	Arithmetic Mean	Variance
Apache OpenMeetings	0.32	0.09
Apache Solr	0.21	0.07
BigBlueButton	0.54	0.11
Google Bazel	0.20	0.06
KeyCloak	0.18	0.04
OpenCMS	0.29	0.10
Openfire	0.31	0.09
Teammates	0.34	0.09
Halo	0.26	0.08
Heritrix	0.66	0.09
OpenTripPlanner	0.31	0.06
Traccar	0.25	0.07
XWiki	0.28	0.12

Table 10.5: The arithmetic mean and variance values regarding the static weight input variables for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

Input Project	Arithmetic Mean	Variance
Apache OpenMeetings	0.30	0.13
Apache Solr	0.09	0.01
BigBlueButton	0.19	0.05
Google Bazel	0.15	0.05
KeyCloak	0.05	0.02
OpenCMS	0.10	0.02
Openfire	0.10	0.03
Teammates	0.07	0.00
Halo	0.08	0.01
Heritrix	0.14	0.03
OpenTripPlanner	0.21	0.05
Traccar	0.16	0.05
XWiki	0.09	0.03

Table 10.6: The arithmetic mean and variance values regarding the semantic weight input variables for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

Input Project	Arithmetic Mean	Variance
Apache OpenMeetings	0.51	0.09
Apache Solr	0.44	0.15
BigBlueButton	0.44	0.10
Google Bazel	0.56	0.08
KeyCloak	0.50	0.09
OpenCMS	0.59	0.10
Openfire	0.37	0.10
Teammates	0.48	0.17
Halo	0.39	0.13
Heritrix	0.31	0.09
OpenTripPlanner	0.41	0.15
Traccar	0.44	0.14
XWiki	0.34	0.09

Table 10.7: The arithmetic mean and variance values regarding the evolutionary weight input variables for input projects showing a similar *Pareto frontier* shape, and ones showing a dissimilar *Pareto frontier* shape

Value	Low-point	Mid-point	High-point
Static Variable	0.0029583	0.4035683	0.7901847
Semantic Variable	0.0000002	0.0144182	0.3441048
Evolutionary Variable	0.6483049	0.9301752	0.8325046
Static Objective	0.4203270	0.4752754	0.5013523
Semantic Objective	0.4335106	0.4971534	0.5657572
Evolutionary Objective	0.8548357	0.8439260	0.8033364
Average Objective	0.5695578	0.6054516	0.6234819
Amount of clusters	90	65	44
Ratio of inter-cluster edge weight	10%	22%	31%

Table 10.8: The results of the low, mid, and high-point of the range of Pareto-optimal solutions, on the example of the *OpenCMS* input project

Figure 10.23: The PoC performance of the entire analysis

All analyzed projects are plotted according to their SLOC and how long the analysis took in total.

Chapter 11

Conclusion

The microservices paradigm is getting more and more traction, while many companies are stuck with monolithic legacy systems that could benefit from being renovated by decomposing them into microservices. However, legacy software is typically difficult to grasp with increasing size. While this process is tedious and very manual for a human, for a computer, it is much easier to oversee the entirety of the application. The area of research of this thesis is still young compared to others in the domain of computer science, as Fritzsche et al. showed in their study on the current situation in this exact area of research. They also concluded that more research is desired to further improve upon existing approaches.

To conclude, we devised a working methodology that generates results in just a few minutes without any manual input, which would have taken hours if done by a human software engineer. Additionally, we fully implemented the devised methodology with a modern graphical user interface that allows for fast analysis runs that yield microservice candidate recommendations in a variety of formats that can be used to assist software engineers with the posed task.

11.1 Contributions

Coming back to the introduction of this thesis and the posed research questions, we devised a full methodology that improves upon similar ones in this area of research in multiple aspects such as:

- A rationale that ties the input to the output to be able to reason about how the generated microservice recommendations are of any relevance owing to the fact that the analyzed input measures common microservice quality metrics extracted from literature.

- The application of said rationale to analyzable software metrics that constitute the foundation of the devised methodology in the form of four software coupling dimensions compared to a maximum of two in previous research in this domain.
- A conducted survey of graph clustering algorithms to identify feasible ones via an extensive set of criteria. Eventually, seven algorithms were selected and incorporated into the methodology compared to a maximum of two in previous research in this domain. Additionally, all of these seven algorithms were evaluated in terms of their suitability for our methodology.
- A full implementation of the devised methodology with a modern graphical user interface that enables a user to quickly analyze input monolithic software.
- A large set of objective metrics that are numeric in nature, to measure the input and output of the methodology to allow for an easy comparison of the chosen graph clustering algorithms as well as the generated microservice candidate recommendations themselves.

11.2 Threats to validity

Missing dynamic coupling The main threat to validity was exhibited in Subsection 9.1.2, which is that the input dimension regarding the *dynamic coupling* cannot be analyzed very well in an experimental environment which decreased the significance of our evaluation. On the other hand, using this input dimension would have expectedly resulted in even less valid results. This problem can just only be fully solved once our methodology is used in a production environment.

Shared code We detected that a shortcoming with our approach is that units of an analyzed code base that are supposed to be shared (i.e., utility classes) will be attributed to one microservice recommendation although its coupling might be equally high toward other ones. This can be mitigated by keeping such units in a separate top-level package or module as our methodology then allows us to ignore it in the analysis via the `basePackageIdentifier` parameter. Hence, in an actual microservice decomposition, one could maintain such code in a *Git Submodule* or transfer it to an internally used library that all the microservices depend on [70].

Quality assessment Just as the other existing methodologies in this area of research such as the ones covered in Chapter 3, the inherent weakness of our methodology is to assess the quality of the generated results. Although we devised objective metrics numeric in nature, the decision if a set of created microservice recommendations is

good is still subjective from the standpoint of the software engineer conducting the decomposition process. There are many possible reasons that a human could decide that certain units of the existing application definitely should not be put into separate services due to security concerns when a network is involved, compliance reasons, etc. Thus, this shortcoming is also addressed in the following section on *Future work*.

11.3 Future work

While the devised methodology is working and fully-functional, three significant improvements were detected, with the first one being an additional evaluation, the second one being a possible feature addition to *Steinmetz*. In contrast, the last one is a follow-up on the methodology exhibited in this thesis. In the following subsections, the three future work improvements are discussed in further detail.

Evaluation study We detected that a useful next step would be to evaluate our methodology with experienced software engineers and software projects that they built or maintain. This type of evaluation would allow us to corroborate the findings of our *Experiment results and discussion* as part of this thesis as an engineer that knows the software that is getting analyzed can assess if the automated output of our methodology matches their expectations. Additionally, we suspect that specific patterns might be detected where our methodology falls short oftentimes compared to the analysis of a human.

Manual reassignment of units to microservices candidates As discussed earlier already, a human software engineer might have a demur in the decisions that *Steinmetz* made. For instance, due to security concerns or compliance reasons, the engineer might have a requirement that specific units of the input monolithic application have to be part of the same microservice (e.g., to avoid communication over a network). Consequently, a feature addition to our methodology and implementation would be that the user can select that specific units should not be divided into separate services. This information can then be incorporated into the analysis by the methodology when generating the microservice candidate recommendations.

Automatically generating API of microservices candidates The other, more substantial follow-up improvement to our methodology is to not only generate the microservice recommendations but to additionally generate the API that would become necessary if the recommendations would actually be implemented. Apart from improving the usefulness of the implementation for a prospective user, this API generation could also be used to automatically detect if the interfaces are efficient and

effective and to otherwise improve them by slightly shifting the boundaries between the units, utilizing an algorithm, to offer a more holistic set of microservice candidate recommendations that can be validated from an additional perspective — the quality of the interfaces between the services.

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